

ZURO

1971

**THE MAGAZINE OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY
UMTALI BOYS' HIGH SCHOOL**

ZURO 1971

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EDITORIAL

One of the questions most frequently asked at school is "What is the purpose of learning history?" It is certainly not merely the learning of facts and figures which will be regurgitated at a later date for the benefit of an examiner. Nor is it to teach us simply about the lives of great men - a view adopted by too many scholars today.

The real answer is far from simple but is possibly best portrayed by Thomas Carlyle who, after writing "The Life and Letters of Oliver Cromwell" explained that in Cromwell he found something of himself. The major reason therefore is probably this: to study the thoughts and actions of men in the past and from this to learn something about humanity in general, with the eventual aim of learning something about oneself. This is naturally on a parallel with the moral motive - the view that it is good to learn about great men and women of the past and thus to learn to discriminate between good and evil, heroism and cowardice, intelligence and stupidity. Not only this but also to realise which one is the better to pursue. If we can realise all this and if we can apply it properly, we can prepare for the future - the future is relevant only in terms of the past.

Turning to the practical context history teaches us not only what decisions to take but how to take them. To be able to do this history supplies us with fields of experience. This does not apply only in the social and political context but in almost every branch of modern learning. Without this experience good literature would not be as great, economics would merely be mathematics, architecture mere engineering and the classics only dead languages. History is in fact the basis for most formal education and thus the circle is full run.

M. Seward

CHAIRMAN'S REPORT

1971 saw the History Society's fourth year of existence. Generally, it has been a good year, in terms of both attendance at meetings and active participation by members in the Society's activities. The year has seen a closer connection with the Umtali Museum Society than in previous years, and it is to be hoped that these ties will be strengthened in the future. It is encouraging to note that paid-up membership has continued to increase and the Society now boasts some fifty-five regular members. Unfortunately, members from Umtali Girls' High School were unable to attend meetings in the latter half of the year.

A wide range of speakers has addressed the Society's meetings, though in general their topics have all focused on Rhodesian history. Amongst the speakers were Mrs Beryl Salt, a radio personality, who gave an entertaining account of her research in producing the radio serial "The Rhodesia Story"; Mr. Findlay, who gave an illustrated talk on "Lobengula's Grave" and Lt.-Col. MacLeod M.P., who presented a talk on "The Structure of Government in Rhodesia". Two meetings were held in conjunction with the Umtali Museum Society, whom we must thank for the use of the Museum facilities. Sister Mary Aquinas, an anthropologist and lecturer at the University, gave an informative talk on "The Zimbabwe Cult", and Mr. Robert Cary put the occupation of Rhodesia into perspective.

An innovation to the Society's calendar has been the inter-school quiz, two of which have been staged with Marymount. Both proved to be most successful and we hope to make them a regular feature with the possibility of incorporating other schools. The Inter-House History Quiz was won for the second successive year by Hill House. An archaeological film evening was well attended, as was the full length film "Mutiny on the Bounty".

As regards outdoor activities, the highlight of the year was a four day trip to Inyanga, where members were able to examine the "slave" pits of Mr. Coventry's farm. A tour of the points of interest in the Inyanga district was equally beneficial. Our thanks are due to Mr. and Mrs. Coventry, and the three girls who accompanied us and did most of the catering. The success of the trip,

both historically and socially, may be gauged by the constructive research that was accomplished and the cheerful spirit that prevailed throughout. A one day trip to Umtali Tribal Trust Land under the guidance of Mr Findlay the District Commissioner, was well supported and evoked a keen interest from members. The abandonment of the Society's proposed canoe-trip down the Zambezi River has been replaced by a more realistic venture, namely a trip down the Pungwe River, similar to that carried out by Frank Johnson and Leander Star Jameson in 1891.

Overall, the Society has enjoyed a varied scope of activities and it is pleasing to note that the 1970 "Zuro" drew favourable comment from "Rhodesiana" magazine.

The sub-committee has completed the first stage of its project on the pre-1900 history of Umtali. In this respect, J. Bekker and E. Smith must be commended for their contributions, which included material from the National Archives. R. Addams, too, has done a great deal to renovate the museum, and to improve the state of exhibits. The Society's congratulations are extended to L. Kok who won the "O" Level History Prize.

I would like to take this opportunity to thank our President, Mr Barnes, for all the work he has done for the Society and for the time he has devoted to its activities, particularly on the Inyanga trip. The Committee, too, has done a competent year's work and I must make special mention of P. Walsh who, as Secretary, has performed a thankless task with quiet efficiency. D. Futter who has had the unenviable post of Treasurer and M. Seward for his editorship of "Zuro". I must include also Patricia Dennington and Sandra Cochrane who have fulfilled the difficult task of liaison with the Umtali Girls' High School admirably. Finally, thanks are due to Mr. McGrath for the interest he has expressed in the Society's functions and Mrs. McGrath who has rendered invaluable assistance in providing teas.

The enthusiasm amongst members in the past year has been encouraging, particularly amongst the lower ranks of the school, a healthy sign for the future. I feel confident that this interest will be sustained, and on behalf of retiring members, I wish the Society every success in its activities in 1972.

H. Clarkson

TREASURER'S REPORT

SEPTEMBER 1970 - SEPTEMBER 1971

D. Futter

The finances of the Society are in a sound state. Taking over this job from Scott at the end of last year I found that after "Zuro" had been published we came out on the debit side of things but this year, thanks to payment of subscriptions and one or two other successful ventures, there is little to fear of this happening again.

This year 55 members have paid subscriptions out of a nominal 89. This is probably due to the amount of excursions the Society has made. The Society was only able to procure one film this year, that of "Mutiny on the Bounty" from which we made a profit of \$12.50 and only one excursion, that to Inyanga, needed to be paid for and we made a profit of \$17.14, the latter of which is to be put into a Camping Fund to procure such items as the Society needs for its excursions.

The following is the income and expenditure account for 1970 - 1971

<u>INCOME</u>		<u>EXPENDITURE</u>	
Subscriptions	§ 27.50	Sister Mary Aquina for address to members	§ 6.00
Film "Mutiny on the Bounty"	37.50	Adams for museum	1.50
Inyanga trip	53.20	Inyanga Trip Expenses	36.06
	<u>§118.20</u>	Film "Mutiny on the Bounty"	25.00
		Petrol for Tribal Trust Lands	2.00
		Stencils for "Zuro"	4.09
			<u>§74.65</u>
		Total Income over Expenditure	<u><u>§43.55</u></u>

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The following are paid-up members of the Society.

M. Berry *+	R. McEwan
E. Smith	S. Cochrane *
I. Gwyther *+	N. Bailey
R. Adams +	A. Elias *+
M. Winwood	J. Bekker +
D. Futter +	C. Swift
M. Wilson	N. Melville
J. Heyns +	M. Taylor
E. Gwyther	E. Kok +

A. Thorne	A. Stead
B. Milne +	S. Scott
P. Dennington	V. Reynolds
C. Johnston	F. Winwood
A. Hinwood +	S. Moriarty
L. Berry *	A. Dickinson
L. Williams	R. Baxter
I. Harrington-Johnson *+	C. Atkins
J. Brown	S. Walker
L. Kok *+	C. Bouer
R. Allen *+	M. Seward *+
G. West +	T. Millar
C. Poulton	G. Newman
P. Kok +	R. Clarkson *+
J. Kockott +	G. Roberts +
J. Whitcroft	G. Chadd
H. Crisp	H. Margesson *
W. Vermaak	P. Weatherdon *+
R. Vermaak *	

* Participated in Inyanga excursion

+ Participated in excursion to Tribal Trust Land

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EARLY DAYS IN UMTALI

(1888 - 1898)

J. Bekker and E. Smith

In the April holidays Bekker and Smith spent three days working in the research room of the National Archives in Salisbury. The following is the result of their work.

Next year the committee plans to cover the period 1898 - 1918. Anyone who has any relevant material or is aware of previously untouched sources of material which the committee may study should contact J. Bekker at the school.

- o O o -

The name of Umtali was given to what was intended to be a town and administrative centre for the area of the Eastern mountains. At the time of Rhodes' first visit in 1892 quite a community of people had already gathered in the Mutare valley. Umtali was the Ndebele-Shangaan form of the name of the Mutare river because Zulu-speaking people use the prefix uM- instead of Mu- and knowing no "R" in their alphabet, they always replaced it with an "L".

FORT HILL

The first centre known as Umtali was the original campsite of Colquhoun and Selous, when they came to make a treaty with the local chief, Mutasa. It was situated halfway up

a hill slope, near the Bartissol mining camp and a rough fort was built there by the police - Fort Hill. This hillside situation was also occupied by a hospital which was established by the Anglican church in three dilapidated huts. A township on the level floor of the valley was the logical development and this move was taking place during Rhodes' first visit.

OLD UMTALI

The town was moved from Fort Hill because it was realised that a village providing for a settlement could not be established on the elevation around the fort and also because mining claims greatly limited any expansion in that area. In 1891 a site was selected along the Mutare (Umtali) river where the Police camp and Government buildings were erected.

A. Tulloch was disbanded from the Pioneer Column after it had reached Salisbury. He travelled from Salisbury to Umtasa's kraal, passing Major Forbes and the mounted cavalry who had just broken up the Portuguese Court Martial of Chief Mutasa. Tulloch then proceeded to Penhalonga where there were 60 men - after one week there were 11 men left. The rest had drifted back to Salisbury. The remaining men formed syndicates in order to have capital for mining. Tulloch's claims were the "Liverpool", "Champion" and "Central Penhalonga". After staking his claims he returned to Salisbury to fetch his wife. He borrowed a wagon to take supplies back to Penhalonga. Tulloch made a road from Fort Hill to what is now Fern-dale farm. Early in 1892 when it was decided to move the town site to what is now Old Umtali, Tulloch got a contract to build a commissal store and the Post Office. The first store was the Manica Trading Company which was followed by G.W. Golding, A.W. Suties and Co., and Deary and Company. The first two hotels were Maritz's and Poulrier's which were just pole and grass structures. These hotels went out of business when the liquor ran out. Later Messrs. Snodgrass and Mitchell built the Royal and Hatfield hotels. Tulloch - "It was a great little town and the inhabitants lived a life of Hope, Energy and Go." The population was 30 - 40 men.

The Umtali Advertiser was published weekly for the first time in December 1893. Local subscriptions were 26/-,

America 36/- and England 32/-. The newspaper was hand-written and the weekly price was 6d.

One of the Nurses at Old Umtali, Rose Blennerhasset, has left an account of the Christmas of 1893 in Umtali. "I do not think it is exaggerating to say that by noon everyone in the place, with the exception of three or four men, was very tipsy indeed. Before the afternoon was spent, the good natural state of drunkenness was replaced by the quarrelsome one. A free-for-all took place round the too-well supplied refreshment wagon". The day had also been set aside for sport with the main street as the main arena. There was a cricket match - Town vs. Country, the latter winning by six runs. All sporting events were organised by a Sports Committee. The most popular sport was Gymkhana riding. There were also athletic meetings and the record for the 100 yards flat was 13.4 secs.

By the 31st of January 1894 the Public buildings had just been completed, improving the general aspect of the town. The buildings were situated at either end of the main street. The Eastern building comprised the Court Room, the Gold Commissioner's office, Civil Commissioner's office, the Magistrate's office and the Post and Telegraph offices. The Western building was occupied by the police and consisted of a Barrack Room, Charge Office, Sergeant's Room, a Kitchen and two cells.

By 1895 Umtali could boast quite an impressive line of buildings facing it's combined Main street and sporting ground. There were four respectable hotels - the Hatfield, run by Mr. Snodgrass and Miss Mitchell, the Avenue, Masaive and the Royal. The hand-written newspaper, the "Umtali Advertiser" was being published by G.B. Mitchell and Company. There were also two bakeries, two butcheries, the Standard and National Banks, a library of 500 books, the Manica Trading Company, Meikles Store and a mineral works plant.

One traveller in Mashonaland referred to Umtali as "The dirtiest and meanest little place in Mashonaland". He also commented on the ridiculously high prices of food stuffs.

During the Matabele and Mashona rebellions of 1896, there was some initial confusion and alarms in Umtali, that Chief Mutasa and the Manyika tribe were going to

join in the rebellion. Signal fires were seen on the surrounding mountains and a defensive laager was formed in Umtali under the control of the Umtali Defence Committee. People streamed into Umtali from outlying farms and mines but no fighting took place.

Also in 1896 Rinderpest broke out in the area. The transport system degenerated from chaotic to disastrous, especially between the raihead Chimoya and Umtali. Rotting carcasses and abandoned wagons littered the trail and even the transport men were eager for an extension of the railway. In fact work was already underway and Rhodes speeded it up, as well as holding a meeting with the people of Umtali on the 26th March 1896.

Removal of township - George Pauling (Commissioner of Public Works)

At the meeting Rhodes told the people of Umtali that the engineers were reluctant to bring the railway line through the town because the easiest way through the Eastern mountains was up the valley of the Munene to its source, across the watershed, then down the valley of the Sakubva stream and so off to Salisbury. Umtali would be left stranded only a few miles away, separated from the line by the high Mubarandanda ridge. It would cost an extra £66,000 to bring the line to Umtali - an extra ten miles of very steep gradients. Instead Rhodes suggested to the people that they move Umtali to the line, offering the people £50,000 cash compensation for the cost of their buildings. The conditions on which it was proposed to move the town from Old Umtali were :-

- (i) That a suitable site be selected on a direct line to the Odzi River.
- (ii) That an exactly similar plan as the old town be laid down on the new town site so that all the owners of stands in the old town would have an exactly corresponding position in the new, and also that sufficient commonage and water be available for the new township.
- (iii) That a valuation be made of the buildings erected in the old township and the B.S.A. Company was to pay the owners of these buildings the amount of the agreed valuation if they considered it reasonable; if not considered reasonable, the B.S.A. Company was

to have the right to erect similar buildings in the new township.

- (iv) The B.S.A. Company was to erect suitable Government buildings and hospital in the new township, and to provide a sum not exceeding £3,000 for water supply if required.

The first selection committee for the new town consisted of Sir Charles Metcalfe, Messrs. Mansergh and Pichet who were Government officials and A.W. Suter as Chairman. The most suitable site for the town was the farms Weirmouth, Devonshire and Waterfall with part of Mountain View and Quaggers Hoek - but Sable valley was finally selected for health reasons. The owners of land in Old Umtali applied to the Surveyor General, Joseph M. Orpen, for land to be surveyed for them at the new site - roughly the size of the land owned in Old Umtali. The new town was surveyed into stands. In cases where stands, held for residential purposes, were found to be unfavourably situated the owners had the option of exchanging them for unsold stands. People could not move to the new site and keep the land in the old site.

On May 1st, 1896, it was suggested that the form of local government - "The Sanitary Board" - was not representative enough and the the move to the new site should be accompanied by a larger and more representative local town body. Early in 1897 the people moved and building operations began. The Company made a clever move in getting all their money back by selling stands at ridiculous prices. Old Umtali was given by Rhodes to Bishop Hartzell for missionary purposes.

A result of the boom in the new town was the Tramway which was amazing for a town of 500 shares. The trip was up the Main Street to the club where the passengers adjourned for drinks. Later this was exploited and trucks for pulling merchandise were used. But this was a hazard to development and to cyclists so it was abolished. Umtali was the only town in Rhodesia with a tramway.

In the first few years there were no less than thirteen hotels, clubs and canteens which were always changing

hands. In 1898 a brewery was established but was not successful due to the duty free import on liquor. The creek where the brewery was first started is still called "Brewery Creek".

The first train reached Umtali from Beira on February 4th, 1898 after leaving the day before. (They had to cut fuel in the neighbouring forests every two or three hours). The railroad was 2ft. gauge. When the train entered Umtali it was decorated with flora from the bush and painted on the screen in front were the words "Now we shan't be long to Cairo." The Railway headquarters were called Paulington. so named in honour of the constructors George Pauling and Co. A banquet was held to celebrate the arrival. It was the railway that kept the town going in the late 1890's.

By September 1898 there were more than two hundred houses and Umtali could boast a hospital, a town-hall and a club house and there were many sporting clubs which catered for the amusement of the people. It also had a library society and from ten to twelve billiard tables. A racecourse had been built and sporting meetings and gymkhanas were held frequently. Umtali was then the halfway halt between Beira and Salisbury and occasionally it was livened up by visits from dramatic companies

DISTRICT SURGEONS AND HOSPITALS

When the Chartered Company first occupied Mashonaland it provided medical care for the pioneers. Several doctors under a surgeon-captain accompanied the colonists and later the Company provided for a few district surgeons. These District Surgeons were appointed wherever the population was large enough to justify their employment. In the small towns the same man was both District and Hospital Surgeon. The work of these men resembled that of similar officials in the Cape Colony. They attended the police force free of charge, looked after staff and inmates of the gaols, visited sick miners and farmers and also had the right to run a private practice. In 1891 Dr. Johnson was the District Surgeon. By the end of 1895 there were two District Surgeons in Umtali. As at the 30th September 1897 there

was : Hospital Surgeon R. McArthy
 District Surgeon F. Appleyard
 One dispenser, one male attendant
 and three nurses.

The hospital in New Umtali was completed in 1898 and was furnished with full equipment and hospital necessities (now Kopje House). It was under Government control. The staff consisted of a Resident Surgeon - Dr. F. Appleyard; Secretary and dispenser - H.B. Watkins; Matron - Miss Bentham and a staff of four nurses. The Matron and nursing staff belonged to the English Church Mission. The main disease in Umtali at the time was malaria and most of the patients received it from the low fever-stricken land towards the coast. The mortality rate in the first year was 8.3%, The District Surgeon for that year was Walter Craven.

MAGISTRATES

In June 1891 an acting magistrate was gazetted to Umtali for the first time. In September of the same year the mining Commissioner was instructed to act as Civil Representative and to deal with various administrative matters. In October 1896 a Civil Commissioner assumed office and became acting magistrate in September 1898 and included the Native areas of Umtali and Makoni. A. Scott-Turner became Umtali's first magistrate in August 1895, (after whom the library is named.)

DEVELOPMENT OF ANGLICAN CHURCH

The Parish of St John the Baptist, Umtali was founded when the Rev. J.R. Sewell took the first appointment in 1891. Old Umtali had two churches in succession before the opening of the third - St. John the Baptist - the first in the new township. It was opened on the 11th September 1898. Before services were held in the Court Room and in the Meikle's brothers store.

AUSTRALIAN CATTLE

At the end of October 1900, 1,000 cattle arrived at Beira from Australia. They were sent direct to Umtali by train in batches of 140 per week. The cattle were obtained through the B.S.A. Company for distribution amongst the local farmers of Umtali. The Mashonaland Railway Com-

Company overhauled and repaired paddocks for these cattle for the price of £78 13.0. Out of the thousand cattle about 980 reached Umtali.

MINING

Mr James Henry Jeffreys was the first white man to discover the Umtali gold fields. In 1888 he discovered the Rezende and Penhalonga mines. Born in London in 1859 Jeffreys arrived in Natal in 1880, and three years later joined the rush to the Barberton goldfields. Jeffreys learnt from a Portuguese doctor in Barberton that a charter granting prospecting rights in the territories of Sofala and Manica had been conceded by the Portuguese government. This particular Portuguese doctor was allotted certain prospecting licences by the new company, but as he had acquired a good profession. he was prepared to share with others the rights he had accrued. Jeffreys formed a syndicate which purchased the concessions granted by the Company. He called the organisation "The Barberton and Manica Syndicate" and lost no time in starting work.

1889 - 1891

The Grand reef, 22 miles S.W. of Old Umtali (close to Odzi) was discovered. This today is the Champion Mine which still has gold.

1892 - 1894

The Penhalonga reef was discovered in 1888. The reef was very long and had good prospects. At this stage the miners on the Grand reef wanted to get cheap power from the Odzi river. The prospect of this mine was considered to have great potential as it was close to the railway.

1894 - 1895

No new discoveries, but the gold belt S.W. of Odzi was discovered to be 30 miles long and 5 miles wide

1897 - 1898

At this stage there were 1,090 claims registered of

which 210 had been abandoned. Revenue was £1,242.13.5d but expenditure was £848.5.11d. The Rezende, Penhalonga and Streatham mines were to give impetus to industry at this stage. The Rezende goldfield was named after Baron Jous de Rezende - "Intendente of Native Affairs". (He was the official who made many difficulties for A.R. Colquhoun, the first Administrator of Mashonaland, at the time of the dispute with the Portuguese respecting the occupation of Manicaland) The most claims were in the Mutare Valley where there were some 160 reefs.

References

"Rhodesian Prehistory" - N. Jones.
 "Bid Time Reborn" - Basil Fuller
 "To the Banks of the Zambezi" - T.V. Bulpin.
 "Rhodesian Dawn" - A. Tulloch.
 "The Rhodesian Advertiser".
 "The Sketch".
 William F. Gibbons.
 Minutes of Holy Name Mission.
 Rev E.I. Sells writing in a pamphlet on Umtali.
 Archive collective files on Adams Hotel, cattle,
 Boundaries, Buildings, District Court, Hospital,
 Railways, Township surveys.

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MUSEUM REPORT

R.G. Addams

The Society has been very fortunate this year in that the donation of exhibits has been substantial. We would particularly like to thank Mr Hulley, in honour of whom we have renamed our small showpiece the "C.M. Hulley Gallery". Our thanks go as well to Mr. A. Leppert, Mr Barker, Mr. N. Bottger and the Electricity Supply Commission.

The Museum was opened on Sports Day and on the day of the Sponsored Swim. The display attracted a large number of visitors.

All the exhibits have now been catalogued. The skeleton found on Rukwerenyanga Hill has been mounted and interred in a separate cabinet built by Mr. Barnes. Now the labels must be re-typed in a more legible manner.

Next year's committee might like to consider opening the museum on weekdays so that more boys may visit it.

A MAP TO SHOW THE NEW
TOWNSHIP AS FIRST
SURVEYED AND OCCUPIED
(SHADED AREA) AND
SUPERIMPOSED ON THE
PRESENT RESIDENTIAL
BOUNDARIES OF UMTALI

PAUSE IN A GHOST TOWN

Cynthia de Villiers

Cynthia spent twelve months in America on a Rotary Exchange Programme and was particularly intrigued with the folk lore of the mountain men of the Colorado Rockies. She writes of her impression of Leadville, Colorado.

- o Oo -

Stepping outdoors
into the snowy night
(on this occasion in-
adequately clad,
since I was intending
only to nip out to
collect the pudding)
was as exhilarating
as taking a cold
shower The

freezing Rocky Mountain air sears the nostrils, and this evening was awchirl with dry powdery snow with which I filled a bowl. It is an age-old winter recipe this, for snow ice-cream, that the miners and trappers and fur traders must have often turned to - maybe cursing the Colorado Rockies for their "nine months of winter and three months of chilly spring" or blessing this bounty of Nature: "Dissolve two cups sugar in three cups of milk. Add berry juice for color and flavour. Stir in enough snow to make a desirable consistency."

Leadville hardly qualifies as a ghost town - its lights twinkled round about as far as I could see through the snow. My family keep an antique shop in a clapboard "salt box" house that they have saved and repainted and when other of the old homes finally find the last winter too much their contents often find their way here. People's chief interest now is in the nearby molybdenum, a heavy silver-grey metal with a very high melting point dug up in the world's largest quantities here. More than 2,000 pounds of ore must be ground and milled to extract 4 pounds of molybdenum and as a result, half of the formidably sized Bartlett Mountain has been excavated away. So Leadville is still a mining

town: its character holds that vehicles give way to people walking - which is an extraordinary sensation anywhere but particularly in modern America.

"Burros" - the miners' donkeys - followed trails through this country last century, braving the fearful aspect of rocky peaks soaring above timberline to over 14,000 feet. gigantic valleys of spruce, fir and lodgepole pine and range after range of stupendous "Never Summer Mountains". It seems that the explorers, fur trappers and gold prospectors quickly utilized Indian food, clothing, shelter, trails, and medicines in order to survive the rigours of the western wilderness. Their vocabulary could not help taking on the taste of the wild, I guess, for they lived on bear meats, pemmican and jerky, huckleberry tea (a few pine needles adds a zippy flavour) and such distinctive resources of the mountain terrain.

The unimaginable beauty of this country in spring must have inspired the men when they crossed tundra and meadowland and forest floors all spread with alpine flowers - like the scarlet "indian paintbrush". But mostly, of course, it was all done for the gold of it. Prospecting hints went like this:

"Exposed veins which are barren will not necessarily contain valuable minerals beneath the overburden.

Conditions favoring the development of a gold deposit in one area may not do so elsewhere.

Placer deposits named after women appear to return a good dollar value. (Any woman's name will do, as the placer doesn't know one from t'other!).

Do not allow grease in goldpan as an oil water combination will float off fine gold. If gold pan is used for cooking, wash with soap and rinse carefully."

They found that trapping required a find knowledge of the wilderness, and set their traps - after throwing them in the creek for several days to wash off the human scent - with gloved hands, digging them into the ground and covering them with leaves,

scattering and carrying off excess dirt for at least two hundred feet around. Ground up fish made good bait: tied in a cloth sack high in a tree in summer to ripen and then sprinkled about the desired area, the odour would draw coyotes, bobcats or lions for miles. When skinning these animals they saved the urine from the bladder of the animal, bottled it, and used its scent to attract similar animals to the trap area. These animals could sometimes be poisoned by killing a deer or cow and treating the carcass with strychnine, but the method was not foolproof since many wild animals apparently had the ability to regurgitate food if it appeared tainted.

In summertime when insects are pesky, they would mix wood ash into a thin paste and rub it on face and arms to reduce insect biting. Out on the prairies travellers had found that smoke from a small smouldering fire of dried buffalo chips (dung) was effective, and here they used green firewood smoke instead. to be on the offensive against flies, gnats and mosquitoes. Then in winter there were the icy conditions to be reckoned with, and they worked out estimates:

A two inch thickness of ice will support the weight of a man,
 Four inches will support a man on horseback,
 Five inches will support a fully loaded wagon and team,
 Eight inches will support a battery of heavily loaded wagons and horses attached,
 Ten inches will support a Texas load of longhorns!

Right then, gold seekers avoided the wide valley lying at the foot of Mount Massive and Mount Elbert (14,433) highest of all Colorado's Rocky Mountain peaks, and the frost shattered backbone of the Mosquito Range lying over on the eastern side. The heavy dark sand

hampered them, and it was not until 1784, when most of Colorado's placer workings had already petered out, that someone found this soil to be almost pure carbonate of lead and silver. Leadville was born like a "Paint Your Wagon" town. The pine-scented hillslopes beckoned at first only men to the dull grinding work of the mines, and then the saloon doors swung ever more frequently and the first (often raciest) girls came to town! Such commercial ventures served excellently to ease a hard life with an illusion of love and luxury.

The pioneer family interwove these practices with those which they introduced. Early women folk brought certain refinements (Some ol' timers contend that things haven't been the same since!). Initially, meals were prepared in fireplaces with a minimum of cooking pitchers and utensils. Later cookstoves were transported west in the wagons. The pioneer family ate vegetables and roasts where only a short time previously, mountain men ate trail bread and jerky (the American equivalent of biltong). Some cabins, though in the beginning built of only crude logs, were elegantly decorated inside, their walls and ceilings covered entirely with fancy wallpaper (freighted from faraway Denver).

Fascinating old pioneer remedies probably died hardest of all especially since a couple of them still sound so convincing: For cleansing teeth, brush with finely pulverised charcoal. Many prefer fine white wood ash. A splintered stick end makes a good brush! A "Summer Tonic" required that one mix honey and vinegar, and a "Spring Tonic" that a teaspoonful of sulphur and one of molasses was mixed with a little cream of tartar as a blood cleanser - to be taken daily until the creek thaws.

As fortunes mounted, imaginations probably turned almost entirely from such mundane occupations as stretching out green hides in the shade in preparation for their tanning, or making jelly jars, drinking glasses or candle

holders out of whiskey bottles. "Leadville" may not intimate the romance and excitement that accompanies the Spanish christenings in some of the mountains (Colorado itself means "The Color Red") or the Indian and Cowboy names of other ghost towns like Firstview and Fairplay and Tincup - but it is a no-nonsense name that a miner can love. Before the turn of the century Leadville became Colorado's second largest city and on olden-day maps you will find it marked along with Paris and London, and will be sure her 24,000 population enjoyed "plenty o' rocks in the box". (i.e. mineral wealth)

Last summer we met an elderly lady in Leadville's heyday opera-house whose memory was warmed to the mention of a certain H.A.W. Tabor. His was among the fortunes made here when lead and silver was first discovered. He was a storekeeper: his shop must have been like the wooden shack with sawdust on the floor that I followed my American sister into, to buy orange pumpkins and Indian corn for Thanksgiving some time later. 'Haw' Tabor "grubstaked" a pair of miners to \$17 worth of groceries (that is, he gave it to them on condition that they would share in any find they might make.) They promptly struck silver and 'Haw' sold his share for a million dollars! He parleyed that into nine million more from other diggings, including one which he made famous, called the Matchless Mine in a gulch just out of town. Tabor, the Silver King millionaire, rose still further to become U.S. Senator. Along the way his eye fell upon beautiful Elizabeth McCourb ('Baby') Doe, and in the scandal, still easily arousing warm discussion in Leadville, he divorced his wife, Augusta (some say she was rather austere), to marry Baby Doe. President Chester A. Aurthur attended their glittering wedding, but Baby Doe was not altogether accepted when she returned to Leadville with 'Haw'. The imposing town Inn and the Opera House both owe something to Tabor's funds and are named after him - they also used to have an interleading passage from Baby Doe's apartment so that she could join him quietly when the lights were down at the opera, and the public were not concerned.

With the repeal of the Sherman Silver Purchase Act, silver prices collapsed and all Colorado staggered under

the Panic of 1893. Tabor's financial and political fortunes plummeted and when he died in 1899 his last council to Baby Doe was "Hang on to the Matchless - it will make millions agains". She faithfully followed his instruction. some say because she believed his prophecy. and some because she felt she ought to pay penance for taking Tabor from his first wife. One feels at seeing her tiny cabin even today that whatever it was her feelings were extreme, for she never moved from her shack beside the now-flooded Matchless Mine, except even as a very old lady to trudge through the snows to Leadville for provisions - her feet bound in burlap (a kind of hessian) against the bitter weather. She lived there until 1935, where at the age of 80, she was found dead one day - frozen and not a penny to her name. The mining people to this day have preserved everything inside as she left it - the great old iron bedstead and brown trunk, cardboard and yellow newspapers covering cracks in the walls of her cabin.

Leadville itself had foundered with Tabor's fortunes, and this time it was a community effort which added a chapter to the town's "striking" history. If they couldn't attract prosperity to the town any other way, why not induce people to come to a winter carnival? Consequently a fairy-story Ice Palace was built atop the town's hill - except it did not happen the way fairy-stories do - and required much hard labour, many beers (to bribe the builders to keep going) and the expenditure of nervous energy of a most unusual kind for Leadville in the hope that the sun would not shine too hot. The structure was fantastically beautiful and hundreds of people visited its inner chambers: too bad the great ice blocks had to melt. Leadville's size has melted away too. There is an old painting of the palace hanging in the rundown entrance hall of the Tabor Inn. Now local kids go skiing and visitors have a look round. But it lives on as a miners' town.

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Several readers have questioned the derivation of the word "Zuro". It is in fact a Shona word meaning "yesterday".

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY HELD ON
30TH OCTOBER, 1970, IN THE LARGE STAFF ROOM.

SPEAKER :
Mr. H.C. Hummel

CHAIRMAN :
R.H. Clarkson

"GERMAN UNIFICATION : A REASSESSMENT"

Economic forces, Mr Hummel emphasised, played an important part in the continuous process of German Unification. Bismarck's statesmanship was supported by the German industrial revolution and Prussia's economic superiority in Europe. The Zollverein for example, had been formed thirty years before Bismarck became Chancellor and was the direct result of Prussia's attempts to establish free trade in Germany on Prussian terms. A treaty signed with Hesse-Damstadt for example gave officials of both countries an equal say and share in revenue, but unpublished clauses made Hesse-Damstadt adopt Prussian weights and measures thereby giving Prussia more power than was outwardly apparent.

Such action provoked an outcry from the other German states but Prussia's economic superiority enabled her to protect her policy from the interference of rival groups. Furthermore Prussia was the largest German state besides Austria and her large labour force, beneficial employment for emancipated serfs, excellent banking system and facilities for stock investment, ready supply of raw materials industrial and technological schools and policy of laissez faire reinforced the legislative advantages of the Zollverein.

By 1865 the Zollverein, as a coal-producer, was second only to Britain. Railway expansion was stimulated by offering high interest rates to railway stock investors. Trade agreements were signed with Holland (1851), Belgium (1852) and Sardinia. In 1857 a federal currency based on the Prussian thaler was introduced - the Austrian florin was withdrawn.

As early as 1834 Metternich was issuing warnings on the threat of Prussia to Austrian supremacy in central Europe. A clash between the two powers was inevitable, and after 1848 Austria attempted to regain

lost ground by establishing a Zollbund. The Zollverein however, remained superior since tariffs were lower and free trade was practised with France.

Mr. Hummel emphasised that Bismarck had no pre-conceived plans for unification - his strength lay in his flexibility and in his ability to manoeuvre a situation so as to satisfy Prussian national interests. This is best illustrated by the Danish War.

The March Patent issued by Denmark on 24th March 1863 called for stronger ties between Denmark and Schleswig and loose ties between Schleswig and Holstein. Nationalist feelings in Germany were aroused and Bismarck realised how the annexation of the Duchies would suit Prussian interests. The North German ports so desperately needed would be gained and Prussia's position and prestige would be elevated. Austria would not want to miss out on the Duchies and would thereby be compelled to treat Prussia with increased consideration, especially as the Prussian king, William I, was not averse to a complete break with Austria. When William refused to attend the Diet called by Austria to consider a scheme for a federal Germany, Austria had no alternative but to fall in line with Prussian plans regarding the Duchies.

With Austria politically isolated Bismarck hastened her economic isolation. Other German states were warned that a refusal to join the Zollverein would result in their economic ruin - they soon joined the Zollverein. Bismarck initiated talks with Prussia concerning military plans to crush Denmark, and Austrian aid was hastened by Napoleon III's proposal to call a Congress to discuss the situation. Russia was pacified by allowing her troops to cross German territory to crush the Polish Revolt. Anglo-French discord over Poland ensured that they would not unite against Prussia.

By August 1865 not only had Schleswig-Holstein been shared out between the allies, but Prussia had proved herself capable of taking the lead in Germany. Realising that a showdown with Austria was inevitable Bismarck set out to secure his home front. Free trade treaties were concluded with England, Belgium, Switzerland and Italy, a diplomatic entente was

secured with France and a military alliance was signed with Italy. In June 1865 Austria had half-heartedly joined the Zollverein but she was left no alternative but to fight if she wanted to regain her supremacy in Germany. Fight she did, and was decisively defeated within seven weeks.

Since 1860 several approaches had been made to the Catholic South German States. These states however, anticipating a rapprochement between Austria and France, supported the expansion of the Zollbund into a Catholic economic league. Prussia's answer was to approach Spain, primarily seeking economic support to counterbalance the Catholic League. Bismarck did not intend to force France into war - events took an unexpected course when Napoleon III objected to the Prussian candidature offered for the vacant Spanish throne. The Ems telegram was an attempt to prevent the Prussian king from adopting a new policy, but the resultant Franco-Prussian war simply hastened the inevitable with the added advantage of eliminating a possible Austro-French alliance.

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY HELD AT THE UMTALI MUSEUM IN CONJUNCTION WITH THE UMTALI MUSEUM SOCIETY ON THURSDAY 25TH FEBRUARY, 1971.

SPEAKER:
Dr. Weinrich

CHAIRMAN:
Mr. J.C. Barnes

ZIMBABWE AND THE HIGH GOD CULT

Dr. Weinrich began by briefly outlining Rhodesian Prehistory. The recovery and examination of implements has led historians to believe that, at the time of the birth of Christ, Rhodesia was inhabited by Bushmen, the last of the Stone Age cultures. They occupied the fertile regions but were eventually pushed into the inhospitable Kalahari Desert by the invasions of a stronger people.

From 0 - 500 A.D. a steady stream of immigrants came south from the Lake Malawi area. Identifiable by their pottery (Ziwa culture) they were superior pastoralists and cattle farmers. Known generally as the "Ancients" they were Boskopoid in race and

those who continued south were met at the Cape by the Portuguese one thousand years later and were termed the Hottentots.

In the sixth century a second wave of immigrants arrived with their origin probably the mines of Ethiopia. Gold, copper and tin were mined and by 900 AD there was a flourishing trade with the Arabs. Archaeological evidence suggests that there was an edifice on the hill at Zimbabwe at this time which was later built over.

In the eleventh century the Bantu arrived from the north, of which the Karanga were the most important. More advanced than their predecessors, they were pastoralists and stone masons and lived in scattered stone enclosures in which pole and daga huts were built. Carbon dating suggests that the first walls of Zimbabwe were erected in 1085 A.D.

Zimbabwe means literally "large stone hut" and was built for the Mambo of the Karanga who remained there in residence. The Mambo had access to a large labour force and hence the dimension of Zimbabwe are imposing :-

The outer wall of the "temple" is 831' long;
it averages 31' in height and 19' in width;
it contains 15,000 tons of stone.

The Karanga established a gold trade with the Arabs and maintained a large standing army, but at Zimbabwe found that the traditional method of obtaining salt (from burnt grass and cattle dung), so necessary to the diet, was insufficient, but that large quantities of salt could be bought from the Arabs on the Zambesi. Hence the Karanga, in about 1450, moved north, and the Mambo gained a new title, Mwene Mutapa (literally "the owner of captives"). Matope, the new Monomotapa, as the title is now spelt, found it difficult to control this empire which stretched from the Gwaai River to the sea, and consequently sent his sons or relatives to control the outlying provinces. A capable son by a lesser wife, Change, was sent to Zimbabwe, and it was he who developed the "temple" and who enlarged the trade with the Arabs. He ruled over the Rozwi and his name lent itself to the traditional Rozwi chief title Changamire ("mire", - an Arab greeting).

It was Changa, a veritable Chaka of his day, who declared Rhodesia's first U.D.I.! As the fortunes of the Monomotapa declined so did those of the Rozwi increase until in the seventeenth century and after the defeat of the Portuguese, the Monomotapa was forced to flee to Tete. Rhodesia was a Rozwi empire for over a century but in 1835 the Rozwi, having grown indolent and lazy, suffered at the hands of the N'guni tribes who were fleeing from Chaka, especially the Angoni, Shangaans and N'debele. The Rozwi were attacked at the centre of their power, Zimbabwe, and fled to Khami where the king was killed. The Rozwi could not rally their forces against the new invaders and they split into three groups - the first remained at Khami, the second moved to Bikita (in the 1960's the government moved them to Gokwe) whilst the third probably went to Barotseland. Some Barotsē maintain today that they are of Rozwi descent, others are more likely to be correct when they say that they come from the Congo.

But it was these Shona-speaking Rozwi whom the first Europeans to Rhodesia encountered east of the N'debele. The N'debele not only despised them but impressed them into slavery.

Dr. Weinrich proceeded with the second aspect of her address, the High God Cult, by comparing the political and religious hierarchies of the African social structure, and she drew some interesting comparisons. At the top of the political hierarchy for example, was the Rozwi king who, surrounded by his Court, ruled for life. He appointed governors to rule the provinces, and the governors in turn held suzerainty over the chiefs. In this way a centralised monarch retained control over an extensive kingdom.

The head of the religious hierarchy was Mwari, (M'limo is the N'debele word for M'wari) who lived at Zimbabwe, although when the King moved to Khami Mwari moved to the Matopos. He was surrounded by Mbonga (roughly translated as "virgins" although many were actually married) and the country was divided into spiritual provinces governed by the "Children of Mwari" (Manyai) - it is they who supposedly organised the rebellions of 1896. These

"children", always men, had to collect tribute for Mwari from every chief every year - and they are still in existence today. Dr. Weinrich suggested that there is a connection between the nationalism of the early 1960's and these spiritual leaders. At a local level, there was the Svikiro ("possessed") or mediums, not to be confused with ancestor spirits. These mediums had "land shrines" where pleas for rain and for help in times of crisis were sent to Mwari. These land shrines exist throughout Central Africa as well as in the Sudan.

Mzilikazi and his N'debele destroyed the existing Rozwi political hierarchy when they arrived but the religious hierarchy remained. After the death of Lobengula neither the N'debele nor the Shona had a king, with the result that the religious monarchy assumed political control as well. The 1896 Rebellions were inspired by Mwari and organised by the Manyai, and apparently in 1896 security forces found ammunition at Zimbabwe.

"Mwari", the earthly representative of God, can be directly translated as "the one who is" or "prostitute", with the former the more likely. In traditional African society the Manyani held important positions but with the defeat of the Rozwi by the N'debele all the best young men of the Mwari cult were lost. The N'debele were soon made aware of the existence of Mwari, but allowed it to exist and in fact used the cult in their subjection of the Shona.

Dr. Weinrich concluded by emphasising that the Mwari cult is very much in evidence today. It poses many problems for Christian leaders but at the same time the parallels between Christianity and the cult provide a framework within which development might take place. One chief for example, was known to resist when told that his two daughters were to train as nuns. When it was explained that in fact nuns were little different to "virgins" in the Mwari cult he acquiesced and allowed them to go. The Catholic Church has even gone so far as to alter its burial rites to merge with Mwari burial rituals.

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY HELD IN
THE STAFF ROOM ON FRIDAY, 5TH FEBRUARY, 1971.

GUEST SPEAKER :
Mr. Findlay, D.C.

CHAIRMAN :
R.H. Clarkson

"LOBENGULA'S GRAVE"

Lobengula, Mr. Findlay began, successor to Mzilikazi, was the second king of the N'debele. Son of Fulata, he had been born in 1837 whilst Mzilikazi was moving north, fleeing from both the Zulu impi and the Boers. Tradition has it that the N'debele moved in two groups and Mzilikazi's main son, Nkulumane, arrived at Bulawayo first and was recognised asking so that the 'Inxwala' ("first fruits ceremony") could be performed. When Mzilikazi eventually arrived he was furious and had the indunas who had recognised Nkulumane put to death. No-one was sure however what happened to Nkulumane - was he also slain or did he escape to Natal?

When Mzilikazi died in 1868 the regent, Mkunbata, had a problem as to whom was to succeed. Two deputations were sent to Natal in search of Nkulumane but by 1870 both had returned empty handed and Lobengula was installed on the throne. The Zwangendabe Regiment contested Lobengula's right to the kingship (as the son of a Swazi wife he was not a pure N'debele) but was convincingly beaten by Lobengula at Inyati.

Lobengula's reign was a troublesome one. Stories of mineral wealth north of the Limpopo were rife (this was the era of diamond discovery in South Africa) and a flood of Europeans pestered Lobengula for prospecting concessions. The most influential of these concessions was the Rudd Concession, whereby all mineral rights were obtained for Rhodes in return for £100 per month, 100 rifles, 100,000 rounds of ammunition and a gunboat on the Zambesi. In 1889 Queen Victoria chartered the B.S.A. Company and on 12th September 1890, the Union Jack was raised in Fort Salisbury.

The indunas pressed Lobengula for permission to attack the whites and it was eventually a raid by an impi into the Victoria district which persuaded Jameson that decisive action was necessary. The story of

the Matabelle War of 1893 is well known and may be briefly summarised. Forces from Fort Victoria and Salisbury met at Iron Mine Hill and left for Bulawayo on 25th October 1893. The Zwayendaba Regiment was routed at the Shangani River and two more regiments, armed with 100 rifles and 1,000 rounds of ammunition, were routed at the Bembezi River. On 4th November a burnt Bulawayo was occupied, but Lobengula had fled. It says much for him that the Europeans living in the Royal Kraal were not molested by the N'debele. A force under Major Forbes pursued Lobengula but turned back after the death of Allan Wilson across the Shangani River.

Mr. Findlay outlined some of the stories about Lobengula's fate. A Mr. Posselt had gained third hand knowledge that Lobengula had been seen in Fort Jameson in 1894 or 1895. A photograph had been taken and was shown to Major Forbes who, upset, suppressed it. Gordon Lancaster, an authority on Angoni tribes, claimed to have seen Lobengula carried across the Manjeni Drift on his way to Fort Jameson. When he died a large rock split and fell but where he died is unknown. Both these theories suggest that the Matabelle King had got as far as Malawi.

In May 1912, Geese wrote to the B.S.A. Company saying that he had three Africans in his employ who were supposed to have seen Lobengula and the chief Induna take poison and die soon after the Shangani massacre. They also claimed to have seen his burial. The Governor, Sir William Milton, instructed him not to publicise this. In August 1914 Geese wrote again to report that Peter Briars, a farmer in the Wankie District, had found the grave. There were the remains of an African in the grave, once seated on a chair, and with various utensils scattered round. In 1913 a man called Van Rooyen had met Briars and had been shown a silver snuff box and a pride which the latter had removed from the grave. Chalmers, another European, was also alleged to have found the grave, but was told to keep quiet. Labuschagne, who grazed cattle in the Bingsa district, met a man called Peter Bray (was this Briars?) who told him that he had two Bushmen on his farm who claimed to have watched the death of Lobengula and who

would take Labuschagne to the grave provided he first shot an elephant for them. According to the Bushmen two indunas, ten commoners and a coloured had been present at the time - Lobengula and the two indunas had killed the commoners as they slept and the indunas were later shot by Lobengula in the cave. The European went to the site and claimed to have seen the bones of ten Africans and found the corpse 29 paces inside the cave and covered in dung. The accuracy of this must be doubted as the bones would soon have been dispersed by wild game and it was normal practice to wrap the body of a chief in black oxskin. There was apparently no money in the cave but Bray removed a Martini-Henny rifle and Labuschagne a bridle.

In 1943 the rain goddess Shoko went to Bulawayo to ask the District Commissioner for a messenger to help her count her cattle. A few days later Shoko was said in fact to be looking for Lobengula's grave. The messenger, Ginyilitshe, had been asked to propitiate the spirits so that Shoko could enter the grave. This he refused to do but said that he knew the grave was there because he had been present at the massacre of Wilson's men. Lobengula had left on horseback with his own party whilst the queen had taken another route in the hope that the Europeans would follow their trail. Two months later the main party was told that the king had committed suicide.

Sioyatcha, who was married to one of Lobengula's daughters, was detailed to accompany the queens after the Shangani massacre. He soon received a message that the Europeans had been defeated and that the queens were to reunite with Lobengula in Pashu's country. He was therefore present at the king's death. Apparently Magwegme, one of the indunas, had previously sworn that should Lobengula die he would commit suicide. Both these men apparently died some four to five hours after taking poison. Magwegme was buried in the ground and Chief Pashu donated a black ox in which the body of Lobengula was wrapped. Sioyatcha said he saw the body carried away but did not see the actual cave.

When the grave was eventually discovered near the Manyenda River it was found to be a shallow cave

with the front and back walled in. There were two poles inside suggesting that the body was carried in the ox skin. There was also wine bottles, rifle parts, saddles, cloth, shoes and some beads wrapped in a Customs Declaration form! Mr. Findlay, together with Mr. Foggins actually entered the cave, but there was much to suggest that the grave had already had its fair share of invaders.

Mr. Findlay showed some photographs of objects removed from the cave. These included a magnifying glass, champagne bottles (the queens had an addiction to champagne!), a mug, beads, a bridle, parts of rifles, pince-nez spectacles, and a pipe reputed to have been given to Lobengula by Queen Victoria (made by Bloomfields of London in 1888). Lobengula had gout and a bottle of St. Jacob's Oil was found in the cave, a lotion which was supposed to work wonders for the disease!

What evidence is there to support the stories of Lobengula's treasure? By the terms of the Rudd Concession the king should have received £5 - 6,000 by the time of his death. The Lippert Concession would have given him £2,000 by 1893. Thus the total was not likely to be more than £10,000. £1,000 was sent as a peace offering before the Shangani massacre. Colenbrander, who found Lobengula's wagons, afterwards bought race horses! The queens drank champagne and Lobengula himself had expensive tastes. Any ivory that might have been buried would since have rotted away. The stories of Lobengula receiving uncut diamonds from Kimberley are more-likely-than-not fabricated, as are therefore the rumours of an extensive horde of treasure.

Mr. Findlay outlined the career of a certain John Henry Jacobs, from whom most of the stories appear to originate. A Hottentot and born in 1842 he was a teacher for the London Missionary Society and fought in the Zulu War of 1879 and the Boer War of 1881. In 1890 he came to Bulawayo and was Lobengula's interpreter. In 1895 he was arrested and sent to the De Beer Convict Settlement. He was released in 1900 and deported from Rhodesia in 1905. In 1909 he was thrown out of N. Rhodesia and in 1918 out of S. Rhodesia again.

In 1905 Van Rooyen of Belingwe claimed to know where the treasure was lying and later a Mr Zeederburg asked the B.S.A. Company for their terms if the treasure was found. Terms were made but no treasure came to light.

In 1907 a Mr MacKensie obtained fourth hand knowledge via Jacobs that there was ivory and gold at Khami. The fort was investigated by the D.C. but no treasure was found. In 1908 Jacobs persuaded a Mr. Suzman to travel around Angola in search of the treasure. After a row between the two Jacobs was deported from N. Rhodesia.

In 1917 Jacobs was back with some South Africans. He reported that there were tins of diamonds near Livingstone and in his claim a Mr. Coetzee valued the diamonds at £3½m. together with 800 gold bars!

In 1921 Willard and Jacobs entered S. Rhodesia to look for the treasure. In 1922 an article in the Sunday Times said that on payment of £250 Jacobs would show anyone the treasure of Lobengula. In 1924 Visser requested permission to enter Rhodesia with Jacobs but was refused. Lloyd in 1926 and Nizzard and Kok in 1929 requested permission to enter with Jacobs - both requests were refused. In 1926 and 1930 Ellis and Jacobs searched illegally for the treasure near the Nuanetsi. Jacobs maintained that all the indunas had been killed to keep secret the whereabouts of the treasure.

In 1937 a Mr. Lightfoot crashed into the sea and was rumoured to be flying out the treasure. The latest application received was in 1966 but Mr. Findlay pointed out that if the treasure was of a personal nature it would go to Lobengula's heirs; if it was of a more general nature it would be liable to taxation.

Mr Findlay concluded by emphasising that the grave has been positively identified by many of the locals, especially the royal Kumalo clan, who feel more free to speak and to invade the area since the grave has been so frequently disturbed and the spirits by now appeased. It would be most sensible now to seal the grave, put a plaque on it and declare it a national monument. One thing is certain - the N'debele themselves take little interest in the cave - their interest

lies with Mzilikazi, not his son Lobengula.

MINUTES OF A COMBINED MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY
AND UMTALI MUSEUM SOCIETY HELD IN THE UMTALI MUSEUM
ON 18TH JUNE, 1971.

GUEST SPEAKER :
Mr. R.W.L. Cary

CHAIRMAN :
R.H. Clarkson

"PUTTING THE OCCUPATION OF
RHODESIA INTO PERSPECTIVE"

Mr. Cary's address was in the nature of a chronological account of the events leading up to the occupation of Rhodesia in which he stressed the political motives behind the eventual march of the Pioneer column. After a brief geographical account of Southern Africa Mr. Cary commented that whereas in 1871 only 10% of Africa was colonised, by 1900 this figure had increased to 90%! The main European countries involved - Britain, France, Portugal, Germany and Belgium - had progressed to the point where only Liberia and Ethiopia were left independent.

The theories as to why this colonisation should have accelerated were varied. One was simply curiosity - the "Dark Continent" was intriguing. Other theories explain colonisation in terms of missionary endeavour, or of investment of surplus capital. Not only was there a population growth in Europe but statesmen like Bismarck were coming under political pressure to acquire colonies. Diplomacy is a consideration - European problems were acted out in Africa, e.g. Fashoda, in the same way as the Middle East is a testing ground for America and Russia today. The economic factor is important - the choice to develop an extensive overseas market as opposed to an intensive home market - but probably most important is the strategic factor, - e.g. British interest in South Africa can be explained almost solely in terms of the importance of the Cape on the sea route to India.

Because the occupation of Rhodesia was a direct result of South African developments Mr. Cary looked first to the land south of the Limpopo. The Transvaal was South Africa's "Cinderella" - a poverty

stricken northern neighbour in the mid-nineteenth century (in 1852 and 1854 Britain signed away the land north of the Orange as an administrative burden) the discovery of diamonds (1867) and gold (1884) in considerable quantities revived considerable interest in this area. At the same time Mauch and Hartley found gold across the Limpopo and the Transvaal suddenly became the province with the greatest potential in Southern Africa.

By 1871 Britain had effectively procured the diamond fields for the Cape but she became aware of a possible link up between either the Transvaal and Germany through S.W.A., or of Portuguese possessions between Angola and Mocambique. Either of these would not only form a barrier to northward advancement but would pose a considerable threat to Britain's hold on the Cape and Natal and therefore on the all-important coast line of South Africa.

Britain encouraged the development of small Republics between the Transvaal and S.W.A. but when Germany officially annexed S.W.A. in 1883 Britain declared a protectorate over Bechuanaland (Botswana). In this way the "Missionaries Road", a corridor to the west of the O.F.S. and Transvaal, was effectively left open but the danger now lay in Transvaal expansion to the north.

In this way Rhodes, prominent in the Cape parliament, was forced to consider the occupation of Rhodesia to counterbalance the power of the Transvaal. Rhodes was not misled by the fabled gold fields of Rhodesia - he used the appeal of gold to attract men to the Pioneer Column. Approaches made by the Transvaal to Lobengula were nullified by the Rudd Concession of 1888 and Rhodes set about effectively occupying the country. Mr. Cary pointed out that the initiative taken by Frank Johnson in establishing the Column has always been accepted, but that this has been based on Johnson's own exaggerated account of the movement. He suggested that Johnson's writings be treated with considerable caution.

Mr. Cary concluded by describing briefly the progress of the Column, the defeat of the N'debele and the establishment of a colony, and by stressing

the political motives behind the occupation of Rhodesia.

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY HELD IN THE STAFF ROOM ON FRIDAY 23RD JULY, 1971.

GUEST SPEAKER :	CHAIRMAN :
Colonel MacLeod, M.P.	R.H. Clarkson

"PARLIAMENT; THE BRITISH EMPIRE AND COMMONWEALTH"

Government, began Col. MacLeod, is an essential part of history. Moses, for example, had given Israel a constitution based on the ten commandments, and King Alfred had given Britain a similar constitution based on the statutes and judgments of the Bible. It worked perfectly and, claimed the speaker, the Rhodesian government had based its constitution on these principle.

Col. Macleod argued that the United Nations Organisation would "mean the end of all of us in Rhodesia and South Africa". The U.N. has more coloured and pagan nations than white Christian ones. Coloured nations are diametrically opposed to democracy whereas Abraham Lincoln's "government of the people, for the people, by the people" is to be admired. Only civilised and law-abiding citizens can make democracy work.

In outlining the forms of government in the world today, the Colonel defined communism as the "brutal suppression" of freedom of speech, action and will. Compare this dictatorship, typified by concentration camps, with our own form of civilised democracy. A centralised government (necessary to prevent chaos), provision for all races, a government election every five years and a controlled policy. In outlining election procedure and speaking of the apportionment of seats in the present parliament, Colonel MacLeod urged his audience to "have the guts" to learn about political issues and to accept the responsibility implicit in every election. Christian civilisation is enhanced by the present government and it is the duty of young Rhodesians to fight to maintain these standards.

Both in the annual meetings of the Rhodesian Front Party and in Parliament the nation is always put first. Col. MacLeod detailed Mr. Philip Smith, Minister of Education, as a fine Rhodesian with integrity, character and patriotism.

Col. MacLeod detailed the work of each Ministry, saying that Rhodesia was divided approximately in half, with one half being allocated to the Africans. The Colonel is on The Select Committee of the African Development Fund and could say that several million dollars were invested annually in the Tribal Trust Lands where there was much arable and grazing land to be developed.

Britain, at the height of Empire, was "just, powerful and fair" - despite recent claims of Nationalists, when Britain ruled there was peace. An excellent example was India, at one time "torn with strife", later taught to live in peaceful co-existence. Britain at this time was ruled by the aristocracy - honest, upright men, they were able rulers who had the "will to govern" and, backed by an efficient army and navy, did so fairly.

In 1914 however, Britain had accepted the challenge thrown out by the German Empire but the cream of her aristocracy was destroyed in the war and those men who had stayed behind, profiteers who made money out of war, came to power. The remainder of the aristocracy were taxed and ousted out of power, and Britains's financial stability rapidly declined. When a second world war emerged "the Appeaser", Neville Chamberlain, failed to realise that "evil must be hammered". The old British spirit prevailed however and the war was won. Once it had ended however, Churchill was "thrown out" by the British electorate - an example, said the Colonel, of an irresponsible electorate. The people are to blame if the right people are not elected to parliament. It was the failure to elect the correct people that had resulted in the decline of the British Empire. As the Bible, the "source of all knowledge and truth", has commanded us, "...thou shalt provide.. able men of truth, hating covetness " as rulers."

A series of questions followed, in answer to

which Colonel MacLeod explained that a fickle British electorate had appeased socialism and in doing so had "won the war but lost the peace", Coloured peoples could not govern efficiently, the Socialists have lost the will to govern - the vacuum created was being filled by the communists. Remnants of the old Britain were to be found in South Africa and Rhodesia where discipline protected the nation against the evils of Lenin and communism. Lenin destroyed the pride of a nation, but this degeneracy had to date left Rhodesia untouched.

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UMTALI BOYS' HIGH SCHOOL HISTORY SOCIETY EXPEDITION
TO INYANGA SOUTH : TUESDAY 24TH - FRIDAY 27TH AUGUST
1971.

R.H. Clarkson

A. BRIEF DIARY OF EVENTS

Tuesday 24th August

Hilary Margesson and myself made an early start from New Year's Gift (Chipinga) to travel into Umtali where we arrived by car at 7.45 a.m. The weather was comparatively cold and misty though in the latter stages of the day it warmed up appreciably. Following the transference of our personal kit into the grey boxes provided, we packed the small school truck. Thirteen enthusiastic historian-cum-archaeologists, attired in a variety of garments, and eagerly anticipating the four days lying ahead, boarded the truck and after a brief stop in town, made their departure in buoyant spirits. The windy trip chilled the initial jocularly and even Berry M - whom we were to learn had an infinite capacity for exercising his insatiable wit - was relatively subdued.

On arrival at Mr. Coventry's farm, "Coolridge", on the Nyamazi River - our base for research - we off-loaded the truck and settled into our extremely comfortable 'domains'. Mr. Coventry then took the trouble to take us on a conducted tour of his farm; we witnessed his vegetables, fruit crop and his water schemes. Lunch at 1.00 p.m. was followed by a brief discourse by Mr. Barnes on the nature of our research and the object of our survey, namely the examination of three previously untouched slave pits, the collection

of any interesting items and the tabulation of our findings. We were then divided into three groups and, armed with digging, measuring and photographic instruments, made our way to the pits, named respectively A, B and C.

We made an initial survey of Pit C with comparatively disappointing results. The drainage point and entrance tunnel were easily discernible though we could not locate the exit point of the former. We unearthed a number of fragments of pottery and a few animal bones, but nothing of particular interest. After making a record of the pit's dimensions and other relevant features, we returned to the homestead for tea, a swim and an impromptu hockey match which proved to be enjoyable.

In the evening we had a braai, followed by a talk by Mr. Barnes on the Prehistory of Inyanga, which gave us a background knowledge to our research. We finally retired shortly after 10 p.m.

Wednesday 25th August

We were awakened very early by the "breakfast chefs" to find that breakfast was only at 7 a.m. After breakfast, our group concentrated their efforts on research work at Pit A. Our prime achievement was the exposure of a "portcullis" in the entrance tunnel. Dense vegetation prohibited any excavation in a neighbouring pit and so we returned to the house for tea, after which the entire group went by truck to the southern end of the farm to investigate additional slave pits. They were all very overgrown; the largest and southernmost proved to be the most interesting as it was situated on a knoll and commanded an excellent view.

On our return, we swam before lunch and then set off to observe the Chiwocuu Ruins, allegedly situated in the mountain ridge forming the north-western farm boundary and overlooking the homestead. We divided into two groups - our party succeeded in losing ourselves and though we had an enjoyable afternoon "bundu-bashing", we achieved little of historical benefit. Mr. Barnes' party located a vast network of concealed caverns and unearthed two complete water clay-pots, the most exciting discovery of the entire

trip.

We arrived back weary, in time for the inevitable cup of tea. Supper in the evening was succeeded by fireside singing and relaxation. Before turning in, everyone went down to the river, where a couple of us, aspiring to the height of madness, swam in the icy water. A welcome hot bath preceded an equally welcome bed.

Thursday 26th August

After breakfast, and having made sandwiches for lunch, we departed on our 'tour' of Inyanga. We left shortly after 8.30 a.m., travelling cross-country to Rhodes Hotel - where we discovered that Rhodes' original study was in the process of being dismantled - and continued to Mare Dam and the Trout Hatcheries, the latter proving to be most interesting and informative. We were shown the various stages of production and the different types of trout. The warden's talk revealed that there were four main types, namely :-

1. The brown trout, a suspicious, quick-moving fish, deceptive and difficult to catch, of European origin;
2. the Rainbow trout, also restless and originally from the West Coast of North America (MacLeod River);
3. the American Brook trout, a sluggish fish, easily caught and from Pennsylvania, U.S.A.; and
4. the "Tiger" trout, a hybrid fish; a cross between the male American Brook and the female Brown trouts. They are disappointing in view of expense of breeding and are gradually being phased out.

The fish are apparently bred for various purposes, notably for fishing - as stock for local streams and the Chimanimani National Park - for local trout farmers and for research in migrating habits.

The next port of call was Nyangwe Fort, a complex structure, crowning a rocky promontory with a steep drop to the streams below the northern and southern sides. We then visited the Pit Structures which have recently been reconstructed by the Historical Monuments Commission. We lunched at the Inyangombe

Swimming Pool before moving on to the Van Niekerk Ruins: a fascinating collection of enclosures in close proximity to Mount Ziwa and surrounded by terraced hillslopes. Our final visit was to the Nyahokwe Field Museum on Ziwa Farm. Time prevented us from going to the village site.

We returned to Inyanga village by way of the Dutch Settlement Road, and after refreshments returned to the Coventry's farm. In all we covered exactly 100 miles; we arrived home at 4.20 and in the evening a game of cricket enabled us to stretch our limbs. After the evening meal, we were treated to a period of joke-telling in which the Berry brothers and Seward excelled.

Friday 27th August

The final day dawned clear though with indications of further rain later in the day (it had rained very slightly during the night). After breakfast we made our final survey of the slave pits; our group made limited progress with Pit B and after failing to locate the drainage point, abandoned our research in favour of the more demanding task of climbing the mountain behind the Coventry's house. We investigated several prominent rocky outcrops, finding only pottery; there was no evidence of rock-painting as we had hoped. On our descent, we went down to the waterfall where we spent an enjoyable and relaxing hour swimming and sun-bathing.

After lunch we reluctantly packed up and said good-bye to the Coventrys. The trip back to Umtali was reasonably short, being livened by much singing and jest. We arrived in town shortly before 4 p.m., having had an entertaining and educationally successful trip.

B. THE PRE-HISTORY OF INYANGA (PRECIS OF A TALK BY MR. BARNES ON THE EVENING OF TUESDAY 24TH AUGUST)

There are two basic time divisions in Inyanga's Pre-history. These are respectively the Stone Age and the Iron Age. The former time period extends back to some 50,000 years ago and was preceded by the so-called "Pebble Culture". The early, late and middle Stone Ages are differentiated by the size and

nature of the weapons. Stone tools became progressively more sophisticated, finer and sharper. Rock painting was an art characteristic of the later Stone Age, circa 8000 B.C., though the earliest surviving paintings are probably not more than 1000 years old. The inhabitants were similar to the contemporary Bushmen, and scattered numbers of these people were still in the Inyangs area as late as 300 years ago.

The commencement of the Iron Age in about the fourth century A.D. was marked by incursions from the north of the Zambezi of relatively civilised people who were pastoralists, cultivated crops, made beads and pottery and smelted gold and iron ore. They lived in settled communities. These people were basically peaceful and were probably the predecessors of the Hottentots at the Cape. Their successors, the Bantu, were very warlike and invaded the country in a series of waves, beginning approximately in the 11th century. The most vigorous was that of the Karanga.

There are four distinct cultures in Inyanga :-

1. ZIWA 300 A.D. - 1100 A.D. One such settlement has been excavated at Mt. Ziwa, hence the name. These people, the "Ancients" or Hottentots, were the first to use iron in Rhodesia. This culture is separated by a long time span from the later cultures; the gap between the 12th century and 18th century is explained by the invasions of the warlike Vakaranga.
2. ZAMBEZI 17TH CENTURY : Only one isolated such ruin exists in Inyanga, namely that on Harleigh Farm.
3. INYANGA UPLANDS 16TH CENTURY - 17TH CENTURY : Characteristic of this culture is the fort near Mare Dam.
4. INYANGA LOWLANDS 17TH CENTURY - 18TH CENTURY : The Coventry's farm is included in this culture, as are the Van Niekerk Ruins.

Several reasons have been advanced for the movement to the lowlands. These briefly are that the climate became too wet, the soils in the highlands were less fertile, and space was limited (some 3000 square miles of land were terraced).

Why should the locals have fled into the Inyanga highlands? Primarily to escape the ravages of the Rozwi who had defeated the Vakaranga and who killed indiscriminately in their bid to check the Portuguese. They (the locals) also wished to escape from the Portuguese people and the Zimba tribe - a cannibalistic people from the north - in addition to the Slave traders, like Gungunyana. One presumes as well that the Inyanga mountains provided an ideal means of protection and fortification in periods of inter-tribal warfare.

C. RESEARCH WORK

Slave Pit C (Ref. diagram)

Description:

Slave Pit C is situated some 200 yards to the southwest of the Coventry's homestead. It lies on a comparatively gentle slope facing north-west and lying adjacent to the mountain range forming the farm boundary.

Because of the slight slope, it is obvious that considerable quantities of soil had to be removed in order to create the pit. Use has been made of a large granite boulder which overhangs the northern side of the pit, which is approximately circular in shape. The ground slopes away from the northern end to the lowest point which forms the drainage exit hole. An entrance tunnel, presumably for livestock, is situated on the eastern side of the pit and is some 23 feet in length. There is evidence of previous hut foundations in the form of rocks in a circular pattern. A couple of quern stones are also evident.

As regards the quality of the stone-work, it must be noted that the rocks have no uniform size and are built up in a very haphazard manner. The quality of the stone-work is very mediocre and any rectangular-shaped blocks are probably due not to artificial shaping, but more likely to rectilinear cleavage (since granite fractures along defined planes). The only possible exception is the "port-cullis" in the roof of the entrance passage, which suggests that when the occasion demanded the builders were capable of stonework of a reasonable quality.

A great number of rocks were used in the construction of the pit, since the height is about 8 to 10 feet and almost all the sides had to be artificially constructed. Packed earth, presumably from the pit itself, constitutes the outer walls, which are now heavily overgrown.

The floor consists of a number of flat stones, overlain by soil and leaves. There is no evidence of a roof ever having covered the pit and hence the importance of a good drainage system.

Excavations:

The entrance tunnel provided the natural objective as regards research work. It was cleared and found to be about 3 feet high and 2 feet wide at its entrance to the pit. It narrowed, but was able to accommodate a human body.

The drainage point was of interest too, in that it followed a well defined path for about 14 feet, but we were unable to locate its point of exit on the outside wall, despite the use of a hose. The exit point on the inside wall measured about 8 inches by 3 inches.

In exposing the floor stones we unearthed several pieces of pottery and a few bones, including a jaw bone and teeth of some small animal, possibly a sheep. Nothing else was located in the pit. Two quern stones were lying above and to the eastern side of the pit.

ANALYSIS

All the pits examined were fundamentally similar in shape and size, as the following table reveals :-

	PIT A	PIT B	PIT C
Diameter of pit	19'	19'	19'
Average depth of pit	9' 10"	7' 4"	8' 6"
Length of entrance passage	25'	24'	23'
Height of entrance passage	3' 7"	3'	4'
Width of entrance passage	1' 10"	1' 6"	2' 8"

PIT C.

TO SHOW THE TYPICAL METHOD OF CONSTRUCTION UTILISING A NATURAL SLOPE

POTTERY AS FOUND AT THE CHIWOCCU RUINS

All the pits on the farm with one exception were located on hill slopes, which suggests that a gradient facilitated construction (see diagram) and made for an efficient drainage system. Hut foundations and the remains of grain bins were evident in the proximity of the pits structures, but the most noticeable was a large (average diameter 16' 0") built over the gap in the roof of the entrance passage. If this gap was built so as to let down a "gate" or "portcullis" once the pit was occupied, then the main hut would appear to be for a guard who would sleep there and would be awakened by any disturbance of that gate.

What then, were the pits used for? The evidence suggests that they were used for the kraaling of small livestock, especially sheep. For example:-

1. the quality of the stone work suggests that the pits were built for practical means with little emphasis on appearance;
2. sheep especially suffer from foot rot, hence the emphasis on drainage;
3. the dimensions of the entrance tunnel are in accordance with this theory, and the pit is such that 80 sheep could comfortably fit into each pit;
4. if they were granaries one would expect to find evidence of daga lining to keep out the damp;
5. if they were for human occupation one would expect to find signs of roofing.

To explain the high concentration of pits in the area one should remember that :-

1. the area is in the Inyanga Lowlands and is comparatively fertile;
2. with the nearby river and mountain streams water was no problem;
3. Inyanga is relatively devoid of caves. Thus the extensive system of caves on Mr. Chiwobuu would provide natural protection in times of crisis.

The Committee of the History Society would like to thank :-

Mr. and Mrs. Coventry for their wonderful hospitality:

the School for the loan of the grey truck;

Mr. and Mrs. Fleming for the loan of the Rotary Camping Equipment:

the girls, especially Sandra Cochrane, who handled the kitchen side of the camp, and the "slaves" who helped so willingly;

the parents who sent numerous additions to our menu;

the six boarders who between them travelled nearly 500 miles to get to Umtali for the trip.

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HISTORY QUIZZES

Three quizzes have been staged this year. Two were against Marymount, both of which were narrowly won by U.B.H.S. with a combined Marymount/U.B.H.S. team coming third.

The Inter-House Quiz was won by Hill, with Palmer one point behind and Crawford, who left their onslaught to the last round, one point behind Palmer.

The Hill House team consisted of Berry M (who contributed 23 of his team's 29 points), Gilmour, Fonda and Kok L.

All credit to Tennis of 2D who twice was able to answer questions which had both the teams and the audience floored!

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EXCURSION TO UMTASA TRIBAL TRUST
LANDS : SEPTEMBER 22ND, 1971

L. Kok, C1.

Twenty three members of the History Society left the school at 8.00 a.m., accompanied by the District Commissioner, Mr. Findlay. Our first stop was at the Umtasa South Tribal Trust Land Council Hall where Mr. Findlay outlined the workings of the Council. An African assembly is called a "dari", and there are daris to deal with most practical needs, as will be outlined later. The Umtasa South Council (Dari de Council) was first established in 1948 but became defunct. It was restarted in 1963 but only became stable in 1966 when the tribesmen began to realise that the Council was essentially for their benefit.

The President of the Council is the D.C., who acts primarily in an advisory capacity. The Chief is the Vice President, and the headmen are automatic members of Council. The T.T.L. is divided into four wards, each of which elects three councillors. The method of election is chosen by the people and ranges from a show of hands to secret ballot. There is a full time Secretary and Treasurer.

Council meets once a month and is divided into committees to deal with such matters as finance, health, public works and local government.

The Council is encouraged to raise its own finance. Government grants are available, especially if the budget is less than \$10,000. Revenue comes from a wide range of sources; e.g. a \$2.00 tax for improvement and development, a 50c dog tax, a 30c dipping tax. The main source of revenue however, is from the Beer Hall - in this instance a profit of \$400 a week is realised.

The money is used for a wide variety of purposes, but the most popular is the building of a clinic. A 50% grant for Government towards the salary of a trained nurse and the provision of drugs enables a high standard to be maintained. Patients must pay cash otherwise treatment is refused - a system which works well in the close African society where there is always someone to aid the needy.

The Council found that education was not a profit-making venture, certainly not in the short run. The fact that the Council is building schools and, now that the Missions are withdrawing from the educational field, is taking over the administration of these schools, is a tribute to their foresight. A 95% Government grant is paid into the teacher's salary, the remaining 5% coming from the pupil (R1.20 per year from each pupil). The schools are regularly inspected, teachers have to be fully qualified, and the enthusiasm of the school children is awe-inspiring!

There are approximately 120 of these councils in Rhodesia, some of which budget for over R500,000. In Umtasa T.T.L. there are five councils, and the council Secretary explained the improvement in the budget figures for his council :-

In 1969 the Beer Hall built on the main road (R400 per week profit and selling Chibuku Beer) replaced a bottle store (R30 per week, built off the main road and selling European beer). Two clinics

were built in 1969, and in 1970 a new school of four classrooms and teachers' houses were built. This year administrative buildings were being erected near the Council Hall to accommodate the rapidly increasing staff.

The party moved on to the Zagore Clinic, which was impressive in its cleanliness. The nurse had trained for four years at Bonda Mission and there was a maternity room attached to the dispensary. The nurse lived on site.

The Beer Hall is divided into two sections, one serving Chibuku, the other European beer. The Chibuku is the more popular and records a 100% profit to the retailer - it costs 8c a quart or 14c a half gallon! Sometimes miniature bottles of gin and brandy (33c) are used to lace the beer. A further advantage of the Beer Hall is that illicit beer brewing becomes unprofitable and therefore decreases.

Back in the truck we headed north to Chief Mutasa's Council Hall. We were astounded to be met by Mutasa's "Skotchikeri" - dating back to the days of Colonel Methuen, wearing kilts, plus black berets complete with a white feather in each, they proceeded to play their reeds, hidden in a cow horn, and which sounded astonishingly like bagpipes.

Chief Mutasa was seated on the dias inside the hall and we heard the traditional greeting of the "Mambo" (Chief) - synchronised clapping followed by mumbled words of praise to the Chief. The Chief is the supreme authority in the area but acts only in conjunction with his elders. He has a number of daris to assist him :-

- (a) Dari de Council
- (b) Dari de Mambo - deals with the administrative side of tribal life.
- (c) Dari de Morswa - deals with civil complaints such as lobola not being paid or the return of lobola after divorce, adultery, the destruction of another man's crops or trespassing.
- (d) Dari Revu, or Dari of the Soil. The African population in this area is 193,000 at the moment, but in twenty years time it

will have doubled. Hence the preservation of the soil is vital and novel methods are necessary to ensure this. If manure is found in a kraal during the growing season, for example, the owner of the kraal can be fined. Goats are discouraged and the Africans are encouraged to eat beef - at present cattle are allowed to grow to fifteen years of age at which stage they are valueless as meat and merely use up valuable grass. Whereas the Government used to spend millions of dollars contouring and then watched the contours fast disappear, now African peggers are employed and the locals dig the contours themselves, on the grounds that he who hurts his back digging a contour is more likely to maintain that contour.

A man who wants to bring a complaint before a dari must first approach his kraalhead (Sabuka) who in turn will approach the headman (Saduna) and hence to the Chief. Similarly the Chief, who is in charge of all the land, will see that everyone gets sufficient land by distributing land first to the Saduna who in turn subdivides this amongst his Sabuka, and finally each Sabuka distributes the land amongst the people of that area.

Before leaving the Hall we saw a "n'ganga" - incorrectly named a witchdoctor, more correctly a herbalist. Professor Michael Gelfand claims the remedies of the n'ganga have no medicinal properties hence the effect is primarily psychological. We were shown the various treatments for stomach ache, diahorrea, backache, headaches, coughing and even abortion!

As we clambered back into the truck the Skotchikeri began playing again and the African women as well as the Chief started to dance. Apparently, given half a chance they will continue all day!

We followed a long twisting road into the Honde Valley (Mutasa North T.T.O.) until we reached the Council Hall of Headman M'pondo. Once again we saw a clinic built by the Council and heard of the plans for a new Council Hall. We were then taken to see a Community Development Project - a bridge which at first sight appeared to lead nowhere but which was

in fact an essential link between the school and the childrens' homes. Each of the forty surrounding kraals put in one day's work and each man brought with him 30c. In this way \$500. was collected and the bridge was quickly finished. Not all the money was used and that which was left over has gone towards the next project, a dip tank.

Mr. Findlay kindly bought us some cool-drinks and we had lunch at a rest camp. After lunch Mr. Findlay emphasised the part the spirits still play in tribal life, and went on to outline the prospects of a career in Internal Affairs.

We were then shown a project which had gone wrong due to lack of adequate supervision. This was an industrial school started by Mr. Sandy Kanyenzi. A maze of buildings, it had once held 700 pupils, most of whom were ill-cared for. Now there are about 300 pupils who pay \$75 per year, but there is still only one qualified teacher - the headmaster. We saw a weaving class using primitive looms but producing quality material; we saw a tailoring class sewing paper as practice; we saw leather-work and woodwork classes.

We returned to Umtali via Odzani and Penhalonga and arrived at school, in fine voice, at 4.45. Altogether it was a tiring but very interesting and most enjoyable excursion.

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HISTORY SOCIETY COMMITTEE, 1972

Chairman	P. Welsh
Hon. Secretary	M. Seward
Hon. Treasurer	D. Futter
Committee Member	G. Roberts
U.G.H.S. Representative	Post not filled
Sub-Committee Chairman	J. Bekker
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i.c. Museum	R. Addams

THE 1896 REBELLION AND MANICALAND

J.C. Barnes

In the numerous articles covering the Matabele and Mashona Rebellions the Eastern Districts are frequently dismissed as of little importance on the grounds that Umtasa did not join the rising. The reasons behind Umtasa's assurances of peace are interesting and will be discussed later, but he was not the only chief in Manicaland. Furthermore a study of the rebellion in Manicaland can throw an interesting light on the risings in other parts of the country.

The symptoms of discontent were evident in Manicaland, as they were in most of Rhodesia, before 1896, yet the belief that the defeat of the Matabele in 1893 and the resulting death of Lobengula had assured an attitude of docility from local tribesmen, prompted most observers of the time to dismiss the unrest as of little consequence. In March, 1896, for example, a letter was published in the Umtali Advertiser commenting on the indiscriminate actions of the native police in controlling outlying areas. The native police of Inyanga apparently claimed to be "At liberty to take what they liked from (the kraal)" on the grounds that as they were not issued with food rations they were obviously to obtain supplies from the surrounding areas. Wholesale demands were therefore made on each and every village visited and villagers showing a reluctance to comply were severely treated. Once the rebellion had broken out Umtasa expressed himself openly on this question of the native police. He argued that the appropriation of food by the police threatened the power of the chief in that he was unable to check it and that the supervisory actions of the police encroached upon the authority of a chief over his people.

Another correspondent, Mr. Charles Hancock, writing in the New Year edition of the Umtali Advertiser of 1895, put his finger on a second trouble spot but again failed to realise the seriousness of the discontent. "The institution of the Hut Tax", he wrote, "has probably brought money into the coffers of the company judging by the successful cattle sales held on this account, but it has done nothing to ease

the scarcity of labour". In October of the same year this scarcity of labour is attributed to a local syndicate which was paying the natives the extravagant salary of £2 per month.

The ravages of nature added to the ravages of authority. There are scattered references to locusts in the year preceeding the outbreak of the rebellion. Together with a long continued drought and excessive heat experienced in the September of 1895, the locusts soon destroyed the young shoots which sprung up after the winter fires. The result was not only a meteoric rise in the price of native grain but also the proposal of various schemes, hare-brained and otherwise, for locust control. 'Breed more hens' was one such proposal, and if this did not work import the Paradise Grackle (grocula tristis) from the Philippine Islands - "a voracious devourer of locusts and grasshoppers". The suggestion that natives be employed to collect locusts eggs was initiated in a more practical form - after all, locusta migratoria were a recognised delicacy with the natives.- and the results were unforeseen, if not amusing. "Mr. Brabant Chief Native Commissioner, whilst in Umtali, was called upon to settle a dispute between Chimbazo and Tshioon, of Umtasa's tribe. The dispute arose out of a locust gathering expedition in which the one held that he had been forestalled in the matter of time of starting. This single matter afterwards led to an assault upon one of Tshioon's men, which was resented, and the two chiefs coming to open combat brought themselves under the notice of the Native Commissioner's department." Both sides were fined all the guns used in the affray.

A.S. Tullock, in a diary yet to be published, described cattle as "the mainstay of our communication with the outside world". To the native, however, cattle were the basis of his wealth, his status in society and his livelihood, and it is in this light that one must consider the rinderpest or Zambesi cattle fever epidemic, of 1896. Mention of the disease in Bechuanaland (March 27th) was accompanied by a report from the Government veterinary surgeon describing the symptoms and post-mortem appearance of the disease. The disease spread

rapidly and by April 3rd (six days after its first mention) it had reached Umtali. On that day Mr. Nesbitt, N.C., destroyed 83 oxen in Leslie's District (the present site of Umtali) in which he found eight to be affected by the disease. Such forcible slaughtering of cattle led to much misunderstanding and ill-feeling amongst the natives.

The infamous Jameson Raid commanded extensive coverage in the publications of the time, but one aspect was missing. No-one stopped to think how the Matabele might react to the defeat of forces commanded by the Administrator of Rhodesia. Dr. Jameson is on record as having said of the Matabele in 1895 ".....when you have once licked them they recognise the fact and give you no more trouble". The Mashona, he predicted, "never had, and never will have, the pluck to fight anybody".

The misunderstanding over the rinderpest cattle killings would appear to be the immediate cause of the rebellion. Published concurrently with the report of the Government Veterinary Surgeon was a twelve inch column reporting the death of five Europeans in the Gwelo area, massacred whilst in the process of destroying infected cattle. Mention is also made of the laagers at Gwelo, Victoria, Charter and Bulawayo, but the reporter surmised that "....the whole thing is much exaggerated". Nonetheless the report, together with rumours of a general rising, had a disquieting effect upon the people of Manicaland, even though the editorial in the Umtali Advertiser on 3rd April warned that the foundation of the rumours lay "only in the imagination of the people themselves". We know now that the initial murders were in fact committed several days before the planned widespread outbreak of the rising, thereby weakening the original impetus and the chances of success of the rebellion.

By the end of March 143 isolated Europeans in Matabeleland had been killed and Umtali, in common with most districts, was declared an affected area by a special Proclamation. A laager was built - barricades were erected around the nucleus of the town (this was of course 'Old Umtali', the move to the present site being completed only in 1897) - and

sandbags were piled around the courthouse. On 3rd April a meeting of the Umtali Volunteers was called at the Court House to discuss the action of Umtasa, who was reported to be using beacon fires to call his men together. Defence was in the hands of Captain Moberly who posted 25 volunteer pickets. The services of the Umtali Volunteers were offered in Matabeleland but were refused on the grounds that their withdrawal might instigate trouble with local native. The residents of Umtali seemed certain from the outset that Umtasa was not going to join the rebellion but those in the districts did not share this faith. On the 10th April C.W. Cronby Dillan complained that the first news prospectors and miners received of rebellion was through the newspaper. Conditions, he argued, were of a sufficiently serious nature to warrant a policeman being sent out to warn the country people.

Umtasa himself was indignant when leading local officials visited his kraal seeking an assurance to support their confidence. He had, he assured them, "not the slightest intention" of taking the offensive. Umtasa's desire to avoid conflict with the whites probably stems back to the days of the Pioneer Column. In 1890 Umtasa had granted a concession to Colquhoun and Selous who acted on behalf of the Chartered Company. Captain Forbes was sent to the kraal to keep Umtasa to his word and arrived in time to conflict with Colonel D'Andrade, the Portuguese Commander at Marcequece and Manuel de Souza, a prazo (estate) holder. Forbes bided his time whilst de Souza with 70 African soldiers hoisted the Portuguese flag in Umtasa's Kraal. On the 15th November Forbes decided on a bold move. Whilst a meeting of European residents in the district was being held in the kraal Forbes disarmed the Portuguese soldiers and with ten men marched into the kraal and arrested the stunned D'Andrade, de Souza and Baron de Rezende. Umtasa was consequently blamed by the English for entertaining the Portuguese, and by the Portuguese for treachery. It was the memory of this incident which persuaded Umtasa to remain peaceful in 1896.

To the anxious people of Umtali Umtasa took on the qualities of a hero whilst Makoni was considered the arch-devil. A story which circulated in 1896 for example, was that when Gururi, a native chief, refused

to rise Makoni's men fastened two blocks of wood either side of his head and set them alight. Badly burned over his head and shoulders, Gururi was allowed to return to his kraal.

50 rifles and 10,000 rounds of ammunition were sent by coach from Umtali to Salisbury but otherwise life continued much as normal. The rinderpest was declining (2,000 cattle had been put in quarantine and 200 shot) the coaches continued to run, the stores were well stocked and the cricket matches between the "Saints" and the "Sinners" continued on a regular basis.

A rising in Lomagundi in early June prompted a new approach to the authorities by the Umtali residents which this time was more successful. On Wednesday June 31 a contingent of volunteers left to join Colonel Plumer in Bulawayo. Captain Turner was in overall command with Captains Moberly and Taylor in charge of their respective sections. They paraded in the main street before leaving and were received by H.H. Judge Vincent. The men did not enlist for any particular length of time - in fact they received a higher pay under the local volunteer regulations than did Colonel Plumer's men and were therefore liable to disbandment at an early date.

Their armament consisted of 80 rifles and combines with 100,000 rounds of ammunition, plus two maxims acquired at Marandellas. To the maxims the Matabele in 1890 had given the onomatopoeic name "isigwagwagwa".

As the Matabele retreated into the Matopos so did the outbreaks in Mashonaland increase. Despite the fact that aggression was not anticipated from either Umtasa or Makoni the situation was clearly worsening. Aggressive action was discredited on the grounds that it would destroy the source of native labour and the native produce market, but one suggestion was to bring the leading chiefs to Umtali to be held as hostages for the friendliness of their men. On 20th June a general meeting of residents was called at the Masonic Lodge to draw up a plan of defence. A committee of ten was appointed under the chairmanship of J.H. Jeffreys, and was immediately asked to send an armed force to Makoni, who was

apparently being urged by a local mondoro (sprit medium) to throw 4,000 men into the rebellion. The committee declined the request and decided instead to retain all horses and men for use in Umtali.

The proclamation of Burgher Law in Umtali - that is all male inhabitants between the ages of 18 and 50 were to assist in maintaining law and order - coincided with a hazardous escape by three men from Marandellas to Headlands in a mule cart. The laager at Headlands was attacked several times but each wave was repulsed without casualties. The defence Committee in Umtali called in the Headlands and Inyanga contingents and the former, none the worse for wear were the following week to challenge A and B troops to a game of cricket!

By July the excitement had momentarily died away and the editorial of the Umtali Advertiser on July 3 urged that an attempt be made to open communications with Salisbury, especially as there were now more than 250 armed men in the district. The ease with which telegraph wire could be cut again resulted in no decision and the matter was left open to be reconsidered on the arrival of Lieut. Col. Alderson.

Meanwhile in Inyanga the "Kaiser Wilhelm" had been sacked and burnt and Mr. H. Newman Smith, who escaped only in what he stood up in, was convinced that the whole country had risen. Similarly the Odzi Store, belonging to F. Clayton, was looted but as the building was entirely deserted it was not taken to be an unfriendly act on Umtasa's part. The murders of Hitchman, Richards and Basson at Nedziew's kraal near Headlands - killed after visiting the kraal in search of food, especially monkey nuts - gave rise to the need for a system whereby all country people could be warned in the event of an attack, especially as the authorities were granting leave of absence from the town to all who could give sufficiently good reasons for such departure. The only solution was a mounted policeman who knew the district - hardly sufficient in the event of a surprise rising - and more families trickled into the laager.

The defence Committee asked the Government to proclaim martial law in Umtali, issued rifles and ammunition to responsible residents, initiated moves

to loan a machine-gun from the Portuguese and prompted merchants to place supplies sufficient for 200 men for one month. In the midst of this activity Lieut. Col. Alderson arrived via Beira with a force of imperial soldiery. Whilst 350 of his men were preparing for an attack on Makoni the local Burgher Force was disbanded and replaced by a volunteer corps, each trooper receiving a salary of ten shillings per day. Major E. Hamilton Browne was late elected as commander. "Maori" Browne was a colourful character - he had fought the Maoris for twelve years, hunted bushrangers in Australia, served as a Papal Zouave, fought the Sioux under Colonel Dodge in America as well as the Galeka and Zulus in Natal and the Matabele in 1893.

Several pleas were made by the Defence Committee to the Resident Magistrate and to Alderson for permission to send a force to reconnect the telegraph line. The entreaties were constantly refused on the grounds that it was necessary to preserve a maximum force in the laager but there was much disquiet in Umtali. The Burghers of the district in fact forwarded a resolution (probably an action which hastened their disbandment) regarding the "apathy of the Chartered Company" with much regret.

The formation of laagers at Melsetter and on the crossing place of the Umvumvumva River by 17th July suggests that the natives in the more southerly districts were following Makoni's example in actively joining the rebellion. In Umtali however, Alderson, followed by the volunteers, rode out determined to establish telegraph stations at Devils Pass, Headlands and Marandellas, with a fourth somewhere between Marandellas and Salisbury. Alderson left 50 men of the York and Lancaster Regiments behind, placed in a small fort which they had constructed as far away from the hills as possible and near to water. In the settlement itself the Umtali Artillery was formed Under Lieut. Fichat, consisting of fifteen men especially enlisted to work the seven pounder in the court-house laager. Capt. Peace, Kings Own Yorkshire Light Infantry, was in charge of the fort whilst H.S. Montagu was the Laager Commandant.

Alderson's column presented a fine sight as it moved out of the settlement. Besides 92 volunteers

he had 230 mounted infantry with two maxims, 39 Royal Engineers, 14 Royal Artillery with two seven-pounders, 48 West Riding Regiment, 17 scouts and 50 wagon conductors, drivers and voorloopers to control the 38 mule and ox wagons. This entourage covered 17 miles in the first day and was closely followed by Matika, a small neighbouring induna who intended taking part in whatever encounter there might prove to be with Makoni. The only incident involved one Lieut. Ross who rode into 200 Mashonas but was saved by the cross fire of Captains Hulley and Taberet and Lieut. Morris.

Alderson made a detour around Devil's Pass (about 12 miles north east of present day Inyazura) and on the evening of the 2nd August arrived at a new police station named Fort Haynes $2\frac{1}{2}$ miles east of the Lesapi Drift. After a night march of 7 miles he reached Makoni's kraal at dawn, achieving complete surprise. The first intimation Makoni had of the European's presence was the bursting of a seven-pounder shell in his kraal. The kraal was in a strong position surrounded by a seven foot wall topped with thorn bushes and containing approximately 300 huts in the numerous inner stockades. After an hour and a half's fighting the kraal was assaulted and carried with the bayonet and after the capture of over 500 cattle, sheep and goats, was burnt. Makoni retired to some nearby caves leaving about sixty dead behind him. Alderson's casualties were seven, three of whom died.

A reconnaissance party found Devil's Pass fortified but deserted. By 6th August the Headlands laager had been re-occupied; on the 8th a large kraal at Macheke was burnt and a meeting established with Captain Nesbitt's force from Salisbury (Captain Nesbitt of Mazoe Patrol fame). The following day the kraals of Gwatzi and Magwendi were burnt and the natives fled to the hills where they had previously taken all stores of grain. On 12th August the two forces left for Salisbury.

On the same day but in Umtali, another dramatic personae appeared on the stage - Major Watts who, with fifty men, had arrived from Bulawayo where negotiations for peace were in progress.

August was the calm before the storm. Certainly there was hardship, but on the 1st September three ox wagons, six mule carts and two donkey wagons were loaded with provision and sent to help the shortage in Salisbury. The mail came through for the first time for seven weeks and, with the natives entrenched in impregnable kraals in the kopjes, it seemed that the rebellion would take a similar course to that in Matabeleland.

Makoni however, after the withdrawal of Alderson's troops from the Lesapi area, re-occupied his kraal claiming that he had in fact repulsed the Europeans. Parties of his marauders made it impossible for the whites to return to their farms with the result that Captain A. Tulloch, with 37 Artillery and B Troop volunteers plus a seven-pounder, left Umtali in an attempt to either secure the chief or deal him a crushing blow.

When attacked, Makoni again retired to the caves with about 100 of his men. Seventy women and eleven men, including his chief adviser and one of his sons, were captured and the walls of his kraal were dynamited.

Tulloch was joined by Major Watts with 155 troops and both men agreed that the capture of Makoni was essential if the rebellion was to be contained. It was decided to use dynamite to dislodge the chief but the placing of the charges proved dangerous as the natives fired unexpectedly from various points. Eventually it was left to Gunner Jenkins to climb down a twenty foot rope, light the fuses and return hand-over-hand up the granite face "as only a sailor can do".

The first charge buried all stores of grain and killed two natives. Watts received information that Makoni would probably try to break out.

He surrounded the caves and five attempts by the natives to escape were thwarted. Eventually Makoni alone came out and under cover of fire kept up by his men above, tried to escape. He was forced to retreat back into the caves but was heroically pursued by Lieut. Fichat who, wielding his revolver, dragged him out from under the very noses of his men. The

capture of Makoni resulted in the surrender of most of his men.

The problem was now what to do with Makoni. Ross, the Native Commissioner at Fort Haynes, thought that to send him to Umtali would entail a strong risk of rescue. Makoni, at a court martial held on the spot, therefore was charged with armed rebellion, found guilty and sentenced to death. A telegraph was sent to the High Commissioner to confirm the sentence but as there was no telegraph post at Fort Haynes the message first had to be sent by runner to Umtali. The chief's fate was sealed that night when his son and two of his indunas escaped - it was decided to carry out the verdict the following day without awaiting for confirmation from Salisbury.

Makoni was shot by a firing squad composed of two men from each detachment. According to one witness this fine looking chief, his face normally dignified and sensual but which could look uncommonly fierce on occasions, died like a man, only calling out to one of his men, "Bury me when I am dead or the curse of God be upon you!" He was buried overlooking the remains of his kraal.

On the 17th September the General officer commanding sent his congratulations to those involved, and it therefore came as a surprise when the High Commissioner at Cape Town, Sir Hercules Robinson, suspended Major Watts for the trial and execution of Makoni. Umtalians, further annoyed because twenty prisoners captured in the engagement had been released without trial, sent a petition to Earl Grey, Administration of Rhodesia, stating that the action of Watts was "not only justifiable but absolutely necessary for the speedy settlement of the rebellion in this district", a sentiment supported by the action of Umtasa who himself came into Umtali to express his loyalty, a journey which he had never made before.

The petition was sympathetically received by the High Commissioner and at the ensuing court of enquiry in Bulawayo on 10th October Major General F. Carrington, Commanding Forces Matabeleland and Mashonaland, decided that Watts had "acted to the best of his judgement in the interests of his force and of the administration of his country".

Resistance was all but at an end. In October a force of about 80 men of the Umtali volunteers, Umtali Artillery and Mashonaland Relief Force, under Captain Pearse followed the line of communication to Salisbury, burning kraals in which there had been any resistance and destroying fortifications.

Four whites were killed, two of them near Gatzi's kraal ten miles from Marandellas where there was six days of fighting. The most unfortunate was Private Hearnshaw of the Umtali Volunteers who was killed by a bullet from his own rifle fired as he jumped over a wall into a kraal.

On 3rd November Tulloch and Fichat returned to Umtali with the Umtali Volunteers and the Umtali Artillery, both of which were immediately disbanded. In Manicaland the rebellion was over although in Mashonaland it was to be another year before the remaining rebel leaders were rounded up. The final act in 1896 before Umtali settled down to its quarrels over the Umtali-Beira railway line and the move to New Umtali, was the establishment of a memorial fund, proceeds to be used to erect a memorial wing to the new Umtali Hospital and to place in the church a suitable memorial window and brass plates recording the names of those killed.

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THE DEFEAT IN MALAYA AND
THE FALL OF SINGAPORE.

M. Berry, C1.

In the Japanese plan, the task of conquering Malaya and Singapore was allotted to General Yamashita's 25th Army - three divisions with supporting troops; a total combat strength of 70,000 and overall strength of 110,000. The three divisions were: the 5th Division under Lt.-Gen. Matsui, the 18th Division under Lt.-Gen. Mataguchi and the Imperial Guards Division under Lt.-Gen. Nishirwra. Of these three, the highly mechanised 5th Division was the most experienced having seen service in China.

The sea transports available however could only

carry about a quarter of these men - a force of 26,000 (17,000 combat troops) from Japan to the north of Malaya where they were to seize the northern airfields. The bulk of Yamashita's army were to move overland through Siam (Thailand).

The Chief Japanese landings were made at Singora and Patani on the Siamese neck of the Malay Peninsula, with four subsidiary landings further north on the coast of Siam. These landings were made in the early hours of the 8th December. The intended British forestalling advance - "Operation Matador" - started too late because of reluctance to cross the frontier before Siam's neutrality had been violated by the Japanese.

By the morning of the 10th December the 5th Division (Matsui) had swung across to the west coast and penetrated the frontier of Malaya, advancing by two roads into Kedah. That day a decisive disaster befell Britain at sea. After the decision in July to cut off Japan's oil supplies Winston Churchill had "realised the formidable effect of the embargoes" and a month later proposed the despatch of a "deterrent" naval force to the East. Accordingly the "Prince of Wales" and the "Repulse" sailed for Singapore - minus the aircraft carrier which was under repairs in Jamaica. These ships reached Singapore on the 2nd December and on the 3rd Admiral Sir Tom Phillips arrived to take command of the Far Eastern Fleet. By midday on the 8th Phillips heard that the Japs were disembarking their troops at Singora and Khota Baru, while covered by at least one battleship (Kongo Class), five cruisers and twenty destroyers. In the late afternoon Phillips sailed north with "Force Z" - two battleships and four destroyers - to strike at the transports, although no air cover could be expected because the northern bases were overrun.

On the 9th however, the cloud cover dispersed and "Force Z" was spotted from the air. Phillips turned south and headed again for Singapore. But that night came a mistaken signal that the Japanese were also landing at Kuantan, so Phillips altered course.

The Japanese were prepared for any signal as

such and their elite pilots of the 22nd Air Flotilla with the best pilots of the naval air arm were sent to intercept the ships. After fighting off one wave the ships were finally overwhelmed by the second - the "Repulse" going down by 1230 and the "Prince of Wales" by 1320 and a destroyer which stayed behind to pick up survivors just after this.

This stroke settled the fate of Malaya and Singapore. The Japanese were able to continue their landings unchecked, and establish air bases ashore. This superiority of their air force over the meagre British and Dutch was decisive in the crumbling of the British troops and enabling their own troops to enter Singapore through the "back door".

From the 10th December onwards the British retreat down the west coast was continuous. Road blocks were overcome by Japanese tanks and artillery or by an outflanking move.

On the night of Sunday 8th February 1942, the two leading divisions of the Jap force which had swept down the 500 mile length of the Malay Peninsula crossed over onto Singapore island after breaking through the last mainland defense position of Johore Bahru.

The attackers crossing was made easy by the British failures to use the beach searchlights, to use the means of communication and to speed up the artillery cover. By the end of the first day 30,000 Japanese had landed. There were two more divisions on the mainland but General Yamashita did not consider he could effectively deploy them in the island advance.

Numerically the defenders had more than enough men to repel the Japanese - Gen. Percival had 85,000 under his command, mainly British and Australian, but the majority were ill trained and ill equipped. It is interesting to note here that only one division was available to try and hold the Japanese right from the Singora landings - the 11th - and these men had fought a retreating action all down the peninsula until, before Singapore, they were practically decimated. The Australians under Gen. Gordon Bennett took over from the 11th at Gemas - the supposed ideal

holding position - but as it turned out it fell just as easily as the others.

The air force had been completely outclassed from the beginning and what remained was withdrawn in the final stage; and the army's long trek down the peninsula had left them demoralised.

At Singapore the end came on Sunday 15th exactly one week after the island landing. (Singapore's population had swollen with 500,000 refugees). Food stocks were running low and the water supply could be cut off at any minute. That evening General Percival went out with a white flag to surrender.

The immediate strategic effects of the loss of Singapore were disastrous, for it was quickly followed by the conquest of Burma and the Dutch East Indies - a two-pronged sweep that brought the Japs dangerously close to India on one flank and Australia on the other. Nearly four years of war were to follow, at immense cost, before Singapore was recovered.

But the longer and wider effects of Singapore's fall were beyond repair. Singapore had been a symbol of western power in the east, especially since that power had been erected and maintained by British sea-power.

The post mortem of the fall of Singapore is none too pleasant. It is full of ifs and whys but the truth was that Singapore would have fallen anyhow. Perhaps with a Montgomery it may have lasted longer but the end result would have been the same. Because of the immediate danger to Britain herself the slender resources available were used on the home front. Singapore was, as it were, at the end of the queue.

In war it is the civilians who suffer. This civilian group was no exception but they suffered exceptionally bad treatment - when the Keripei (Tojos Military Secret Police) moved in the spate of murders and tortures went on for weeks. The bayoneting of live victims was commonplace.

The army also suffered - either by being sent to Chongi Prison camp under General Saito or by being sent to build the Burma railway - in which a man died

for every sleeper laid.

But the eventual allied victory over Japan proved one thing - the place of the white man in the Far East would never be the same again. The white man was out of place in the east and the cost of maintaining these possessions was momentous, it further became obvious that Singapore and the Malay states would soon gain their freedom. At present they are at peace so perhaps the loss of the colonies was not a failure after all.

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YESTERDAY AND TODAY

A talk given to the History Society by Mr.C.M. Hulley.

The other day I decided to take a leisurely walk through your school grounds; I entered by a small gate from the main road.

At each sports ground I halted and admired what I saw. The grass was beautifully cut and green. Seating arrangements in a pavilion were being prepared for coming sports and every detail had been carefully planned. There was a running track, beautifully laid out. Every detail had been thought of. Leading from the ground were stone steps, well constructed. They led to another playing field. On this ground a cricket match was in progress. And it was delightful to see the white figures on the field, the enthusiasm and enjoyment of the players and spectators. There seemed to be magnificent playing fields wherever I looked, and the situation was superb, for below me the town nestled amongst large green trees, and beyond that was a panorama of blue hills extending away into the distance. It was difficult to take this all in. Sitting down on the lush grass, I began to think of Umtali as it used to be and I began to make comparisons. To make comparisons is always somewhat saddening. When one thinks of the past one immediately realizes the great privilege one has had in seeing a new country like Rhodesia growing up, - developing.

Naturally the modern schools have wonderful advantages over the old pioneer educational efforts. They had to make do with what they had on hand. Not that they were unhappy or envious of others, but it is only when one realises the big advantages that the modern child has that one feels sad - the pioneer children had limited educational benefits. Take Umfoli for instance; the population was less than a hundred and we children had no playing fields. We were quite content to play cricket and football on roads or any suitable clearing. The schools themselves were isolated, and in areas around them the grass was roughly cut or grazed off by cattle, horses or donkeys. In those days the Sanitary Board, which preceded the Municipality, had no objections to animals being kept in town. The cricket pitch we badzared ourselves and smoothed it down with spades. It was all very primitive but it sufficed and many an exciting match was played by picking teams amongst ourselves. Visiting teams were not heard of in those days. Naturally bowling and batting were difficult owing to the terrain of the pitch. Equipment was very hard to come by, two bats being a luxury and the trouble we had in keeping those bats in order, binding them with string when they were damaged. If by chance the handle came apart from the block, then gluing was necessary, and the bat was out of commission for some time. The cricket ball itself was a responsibility for not only did it get lost in the long grass but it broke open every now and again. Fortunately we had an old native messenger, named Nyamonda, who saw to Father's horses and also repaired the harness when necessary. So the cricket ball was taken to him. He produced a buck skin very well tanned and very pliable. With a sharp knife he cut thin strips from it, and with a treadle and a needle he stiched our cricket ball up. The ball was not exactly round after being repaired but it was serviceable. The strips taken from the hide not only repaired harness and cricket balls but made excellent boot laces. Cricket pads, gloves, etc. were unattainable. Now can you see the comparison between now and then? The wonderful playing fields before me, beautifully laid out. No wonder within me

was a feeling of regret at not having had the opportunity of playing games as they should be played and I wondered if these young people of today ever stopped to think. Did they appreciate the great advantages they possessed?

No good thinking over these things, I got up and walked on, but thoughts have a habit of always persisting. I walked past excellent tennis courts, and these too brought back memories of the past. I was living on a farm at one time in the early days. We were very hard up after a severe tobacco slump. Our neighbours were in the same plight. There was very little to take our minds of our troubles. I was discussing this with my wife one morning, and she too was feeling the strain of having no diversions whatever. Suddenly she said, "If we only had a tennis court, what a God-send it would be "

"That's an idea," I agreed. "We have some old racquets and balls which have not been in use for years, but they'll come in handy and I expect our neighbours may have a racquet or two. All we want now is a tennis court, and that's easy! Why not invite our friends on Saturday?"

The day was Wednesday and I had undertaken to complete a tennis court in three days. Surely a record.

My wife was rather dubious at the time limit. But her enthusiasm got the better of her, and she dispatched the invitations.

The neighbours accepted and were overwhelmed by the thought of a game of tennis. "Marvellous!" was the instant reply.

I started work on the court immediately. The African labourers were summoned and arrived bewildered and somewhat resentful that a piece of good ground should be used to knock a ball about on when it could be used to grow good mealies.

Fortunately there was a fairly level piece of ground near the homestead; the grass was carefully removed with hoes. There was no roller so the ground was smoothed off by pulling a heavy piece

of railway line, drawn by oxen, backwards and forwards. The result was amazing and I was delighted to see what was being accomplished. After the loose ground was swept away, a few ridges and holes were dealt with. The lines were carefully marked out with lime. Arrangements for the net were simplified by planting a pole on each side of the court. In the meantime my wife had appropriated a length of hessian from my shed and stitched a seam along the top of it. This served admirably as a net. Through the seam a wire was threaded, one end fastened to one pole. With the aid of an old wagon brake attached to the opposite pole the tension height was manipulated most successfully. Finally a fence of gum poles and thatch were substituted for wire netting around the court, this prevented the balls from disappearing into the bundu. The court was completed within the time limit and my wife and I looked on it with pride.

Now you have full instructions how to make a court!

On the appointed day the neighbours arrived full of enthusiasm and appreciation, marvelling at what had been done in so short a time. Many an exciting game was played after that and it was most successful.

Now, looking at these wonderful courts before me, I wondered if the players appreciated their courts as much as we did ours. Oh, I do hope so!

It was a wonderful day - the sun shining brightly as I walked on, and then I came to a magnificent swimming pool. The sun reflected the sky into the clear blue water. There were no swimmers present but here seemed something unique before me. I marvelled at the opportunities given to youth today. These waters not only kept their bodies fresh and pure but developed their stamina and stimulated them. The enjoyment they must receive in swimming and competing with each other must be immense. Looking on the other side of the coin the past crept into my mind and saddened me. The pools and streams round Umtali at one time were infected with bilharzia and we swam and wallowed in them, as there were no swimming baths. But alas the seed of ill

health was being planted in those young bodies, and many of them suffered ill health afterwards. I thanked God that these young people were able to swim in clear fresh water and there was no dread of any infection lurking near.

I moved on, and the next thing that caught my mind was a stationary bus which brought a number of people to and from school. Transport naturally was an important item and here again the modern child has many advantages. There are cars and cycles to be had to bring them right from the doors of their houses to their schools. What a contrast to the old days! They arrived mainly on foot, boys and girls walking for miles as the school was some distance from their homes. The more fortunate had horses to ride but quite a few arrived on donkeys. When it was possible parents dropped their children at the school, their transport being carts drawn by horses, mules and even donkeys. Cycles were few and far between. Early cycles were without free-wheels and it was a common sight to see a cycle tearing down Main Street with the rider's feet up on the rests on each side of the front fork and the pedals revolving round at a great speed. Transport was always a difficulty in those days. But difficulties did not deter anyone. The children just took it for granted that if there was no transport they must walk and to walk was not a problem or an obstacle to worry about. After all, their homes too were rather primitive, materials were very difficult to obtain. These people face discomforts, but determination got them through. Our parents in the early days were very deft with their hands. Tables and chairs were contrived out of packing cases, and boxes made excellent cupboards. The women-folk vied for supremacy in producing the daintiest rooms in their home-making efforts. A glance back at Old Umtali. Then homes were built with anything they could lay their hands on. As time went on the buildings constructed from wattle & daub vanished and brick-thatch took their place. Then gradually the iron roofs took the place of thatch ones but there were very few of these, as you must remember there were no trains at the time, and transport had to be

done by ox wagon and all materials brought from South Africa. When New Umtali came into being and the trains arrived the old temporary buildings were replaced by more modern buildings, such as wood and iron on pillars, and many of these old houses can be seen in Umtali today. As Rhodesian Railways were administered from Umtali and there were also large railway repairing workshops in Umtali, it was essential that the staff be housed and as these wood and iron buildings could be erected in a very short time, they sprung up like mushrooms.

Naturally builders were in big demand and quite a few found themselves in jail owing to alcoholic orgies. The Magistrate however remedied this by allowing them to work during the day on condition they reported to the jail warden every evening. So at sundown a pathetic crowd could be seen knocking at the jail door seeking admission as time was running out. I moved on. Not far off were impressive school buildings, the architecture and the planning of these buildings was excellent. Their windows give one the impression that the interior was airy and bright. All the school buildings, halls, and dormitories were delightfully up to date. The first concern in construction was to admit simple fresh air. It was essential within these walls not only that education was being considered but health. It was all taking place in the right environment. Here where the buildings that were producing the right citizens for Rhodesia. And when I thought of the first mud and daub school in Old Umtali, I marvelled at how far advanced education had progressed. The schools of the past and present had left their mark as a great many of the scholars achieved what was expected of them and are now in prominent positions all over Rhodesia. There is just one more place to visit before I mend my way back. I climbed the hill at the back of the school and here I found the key to the whole situation for here is a beautiful chapel and a fountain playing not far from it; lovely flowers grew round it profusely. What better monument to these young lads who gave their lives for their country. Here the past and future united in beautiful surroundings. A chapel which overlooks

the whole of Umtali, the Vumba mountains and other mountains and peaks which extend far into the distance. It overlooks a modern town with its modern buildings, its large Civic Centre, its theatres, its spacious Queen's Hall. Hospitals and ideal homes surrounded by gracious trees, shrubs and flowers. The chapel itself, unique in construction, stands majestically on top of the hill. It represents the past and present, for looking through the open doors a large cross can be seen above the altar. Looking through the massive windows, beyond can be seen another cross on a lonely hill. Another monument denoting that others too had died for their country. In the two world wars Rhodesians had responded to the call. Men downed their tools, offices closed, doors were locked up as they went to enrol. Only old men and women and children remained. The stir came when Britain asked for help. The call was not disregarded but answered in full. Rhodesia and other countries were in peril. So the men and women fought and died. Many returned disabled and many were in a quandry as it meant readjustment to their lives, for years of service had changed their outlook and had either made or marred them.

And now before us is the chapel which reminds us of the work that has been done and the work still to be done.

"EX MONTIBUS ROBUR" (My Latin is very rusty, but I think this means "Out of the mountains - strength") and we Rhodesians young and old will go on from strength to strength. But remember "that without vision, the people perish".

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WHAT I WOULD DO IF I WERE MAYOR OR CHAIRMAN OF MY LOCAL COUNCIL

Pat Dennington

Pat, a member of both the History Society Committee and the Sub-committee, won the Rhodesia Local Government Competition. This is her answer to the last question, an essay limited to 750 words.

Possibly the greatest problem our local authority faces is the lack of housing for both European and African residents. The Europeans most affected are the new immigrants to the town both from abroad and other Rhodesian centres. There is a shortage of houses available for rental to accommodate them until they can find a suitable property. Single people also have no means of renting flats on a long term basis.

If I were Mayor I would actively propose to the government the development of government sponsored housing schemes. These would entail estates of small, partially furnished houses leased at a reasonable rent by new residents for periods of six months to a year, by which time the occupiers must have found a suitable property. Alternately, or in accordance with these, blocks of partially furnished flats could be constructed and rented under similar terms.

To cater for the requisites of single people or newly-weds there should be more flats available in the town for rental on a long lease system and charging normal rates. These would also be suitable for older people who do not want the costs and work involved in running a family residence.

African housing is very short in Umtali. To cater for this necessity, the local authorities ought to make the larger concerns responsible for the housing of their African employees. This would involve the allocation of certain areas in the district around Umtali, where land would be purchased at a reduced cost and such a scheme could be carried out. The initial construction cost would be considerable for the large concerns but it would ease the shortage. Government housing should also be extended, using if necessary funds from the African Beer Profits.

Another local problem is the maintenance of roads. The Vumba road in particular is in dire need of repair and though the Council has forecast its reconstruction, work has not begun as yet. Such undertakings should be contracted out to private enterprise which would complete the work in shorter time and maintain a higher standard than Municipal workers. This was shown by the Christmas Pass Road which did not prove to be a hundred per cent satisfactory.

Umtali needs to attract industrial and business enterprises to prosper and encourage further investment. Much could be done to attract more industries such as offering reduced water and electricity tariffs, having special railway concessions for cheap transport of finished products and allowing cheaper land to build on. In this context, the government housing scheme would be an added incentive as employees could be initially accommodated.

Another problem the local authority has to face is how to dissuade its younger citizens from leaving the town for Salisbury or foreign countries. Umtali lacks sufficient entertainment for young as well as old people. Television in this respect would be a great help in passing the lonely evenings. If I were Mayor, I would clamour for television to be supplied to Umtali. Smaller centres than Umtali have television services and though the problem of site and the difficulty of obtaining equipment holds up the project, I would make direct representations to have it supplied as soon as was possible. This and availability of rented flats might deter young people from moving away.

The Umtali municipality is also in need of further expansion to its sewerage works as the three existing sewerage farms are grossly overworked. As this is a necessary facility for the town, I as Mayor would see that further extensions were constructed.

Umtali has a great responsibility towards its outlying districts. At the moment not all of them are supplied with mains electricity and still less have municipal water supplies. Such essential services should be supplied to them and as Mayor I would approach government to subsidise further schemes in this direction.

The care of old people poses problems for the local authority. Accommodation is limited at the moment though new housing schemes are underway. I would see that these were extended. Old people should also have subsidised facilities - cheaper entrances to theatre and cinemas, minimum rents, reduced electricity and water rates and cheaper transport costs if they were not financially able to afford them. The

care of the older people is of national importance thus requests would be made to the government for financial assistance in this problem.

Schooling in Untali is sufficient for the local residents but for out of town people who need boarding places, these are not sufficient. As Mayor I would approach the Ministry of Education to extend boarding facilities in the schools.

These are Untali's main problems which are not easily solved. Finance is the one restriction to improvements and if I were Mayor, I would find that propositions are one thing, but application is another.

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